

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Into-DIALOGUE

Deliverable 2.2

Farmers needs with a focus on soil

Version 2.0

Due date of deliverable: M47 (December 2023)
Actual submission date (Version 2.0) (31-10-2024)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695

GENERAL DATA

Proposal for EJP SOIL 3rd Internal Call topic: CA4/SP3-2-Fostering the adoption of agroecological system for climate change mitigation and adaptation and sustainable agricultural production

Project title: More than a Dialogue between actors, seeking the integration of soil-based principles in agroecological systems

Project website: <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/eom4soil/into-dialogue>

Coordinator: Sabina Asins-Velis (CSIC-Spain), Co-Coordinator: Akin Ün (TAGEM-Turkey)

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: D2.2

DELIVERABLE TITLE: Farmers needs with a focus on soil

DELIVERABLE TYPE: Report

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER: WP2

WP LEADERS: Anita Maienza (CNR) and Jerzy Grabinski (IUNG)

WORK PACKAGE TITLE: Farmers vision on soil properties and soil management practices to achieve sustainable agroecological systems

TASK NUMBER 2.2

TASK TITLE: Farmers needs with a focus on soil

TASK LEADERS: Gabriele Buttafuoco (CNR) and Kristīne Afanasjeva (UL)

TEAM: Gabriele Buttafuoco (CNR), Kristīne Afanasjeva (UL), Sabina Asins (CSIC), Akin Ün (TAGEM), Anita Maienza (CNR), Jerzy Grabinski (IUNG), Gherardo Biancofiore (CNR), Mario Cariello (CREA), Giovanni Dara Guccione (CREA), Sara Di Lonardo Sara (CNR), Pavel Fuksa (CZU), Raimonds Kasparinskis (UL), Michelle Kushnir (CZU), Erica Lumini (CNR), Ieva Mockeviciene (LAMMC), Martin Pisarčík (CZU), Monika Vikiene (LAMMC)

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1. Introduction and objectives

Agroecology is a transdisciplinary science that applies ecological concepts to agri-food systems through individual and collective action. An important part of agroecology is a socio-economic dimension co-creating knowledge with stakeholders, building connections between producers, and consumers and reducing social injustice (Bezner Kerr et al., 2023). Although, the long-standing term “agroecology” varies in different contexts it assembles different perspectives emphasizing the need to involve scientists, policymakers, and practitioners in the decision-making process in agriculture and the entire food system (Friedrich et al., 2024).

Agroecology as an approach integrates ecological processes and provides resilience to agrosystems while minimizing soil degradation, water contamination, greenhouse gas emissions, and exhaustion of non-renewable resources and thus reducing possible future costs (Bezner Kerr et al., 2021). Being part of sustainable management agroecological practices diversifies landscape and farming (Bezner Kerr et al., 2023), implements biodiversity-based solutions (Boeraeve et al., 2022), and supports fertile soil and its structure by increasing soil organic matter to improve soil biota and its related nutrient cycling and natural regulation of diseases (Chabert and Sarthou, 2020). Some other practices are reducing tillage, eliminating chemical synthesized fertilizers and pesticides (Boeraeve et al., 2022), instead adding organic amendments, intercropping, crop and pasture rotation, cover crops, silvopasture, integrated aquaculture, (Bezner Kerr et al., 2023) and conserving semi-natural habitats to increase the diversity of pollinators and natural enemies of pests to encourage natural control of pests, diseases and weeds (Chabert and Sarthou, 2020). While it is necessary to apply individual solutions and place-based knowledge for local issues, overall agroecology positively impacts the environment, economy, human health, and social aspects (Friedrich et al., 2024).

The report provides insights into farmers' soil-related needs and their willingness to adopt sustainable agroecological practices across seven participating countries involved in the INTO-DIALOGUE project: (Czechia (CZ), Italy (IT), Latvia (LV), Lithuania (LT), Poland (PL), Spain (ES), and Turkey (TR)). The activity reported in this deliverable contributes to the fulfilment of Objective 2.2 “Soil indicators identification and transfer” and provides the soil-related needs of farmers and the lack of awareness of not adopting agroecological practices to be included in the WP3 within the results on the ecological identity of the farmers.

The **objective** of the questionnaire is to assess and understand the ecological identity of farmers in the designated countries, focusing specifically on identifying their soil-related needs and evaluating their level of awareness regarding the adoption of agroecological practices.

2. Methodology

2.1. Research design

This questionnaire aimed to assess and characterize the agroecological identity of farmers from seven countries (Czechia, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Spain, and Turkey) that participated in the Into-DIALOGUE project, evaluating their awareness and understanding of agroecological practices, identifying barriers and facilitators to adoption, and assessing the impact of these practices on soil-related challenges. The questionnaire was developed based on a review of existing literature on agroecological practices, farming challenges, and farmer's identity.

The questionnaire consists of **five sections** designed to gather data (Appendix 1):

2.1.1. Section 1. Demographic Information

This section gathers essential background data on participants to contextualize responses. Information gathered in this section includes respondents' age, gender, educational background, and farming experience to create a detailed demographic profile. It also captures geographical context, including country and environmental zone classification according to Metzger et al. (2005) (Appendix 2), along with key farm-related details such as farm size and agricultural area utilization, classified according to Eurostat standards. This foundational data allows for the categorization of diverse farm types and management practices, helping to contextualize each respondent's background and farming environment. In this section, most questions were single-choice, except for agricultural area utilization and livestock types, which were multiple-choice to account for farmers often having multiple land uses and livestock types.

2.1.2. Section 2. Ecological Identity

This section evaluates farmers' perceptions of agroecological practices and how they view their farming methods concerning to environmental sustainability. It includes questions on farmers' familiarity with agroecological practices, their perceived importance, and the specific practices they identify as agroecological (e.g., crop rotation, cover crops, agroforestry). Participants also rate how environmentally friendly they believe their practices are. This information helps assess how aligned farmers' self-identified practices are with established agroecological methods, providing insights into their ecological identity. The questions on environmental friendliness, significance of agroecological practices, and familiarity with agroecological definitions were single-choice. In contrast, identifying agroecological practices from a provided list allowed multiple choices, as did selecting practices relevant to respondents' farms.

2.1.3. Section 3. Awareness of Agroecological Practices

This section evaluates farmers' knowledge of specific agroecological practices by prompting them to assess their familiarity with these practices. A comprehensive list of agroecological practices, along with their definitions, is provided in Appendix 3. Familiarity is measured using a Likert scale, allowing for a nuanced understanding of how well farmers recognize and understand these practices. Furthermore, this section investigates whether farmers have participated in any training or educational programs related to agroecological practices. It inquires about the sources of information they utilize and the specific topics covered during their training, employing open-ended questions to capture detailed responses. Additionally, information was gathered regarding where farmers typically seek information about agricultural practices, utilizing a multiple-choice questionnaire to identify the most common sources.

2.1.4. Section 4. Barriers and Facilitators

This section assesses the likelihood of farmers adopting agroecological practices by evaluating the challenges and barriers they encounter during the adoption process. Respondents were asked to evaluate several potential barriers, including lack of knowledge, limited financial resources, and insufficient institutional support. Conversely, farmers were also queried about the facilities or factors that could facilitate the adoption of agroecological practices. Potential facilitators included access to financial incentives, availability of training programs, supportive policies, and demonstrated success from peers in the farming community. Both barriers and facilitators were assessed using a Likert scale, with a rating of 1 indicating “Not a challenge”/ “Not important” and a rating of 5 indicating a “Significant challenge”/ “Extremely important”.

2.1.5. Section 5. Soil-Related Challenges

This section prompts farmers to evaluate the agroecological practices they consider most effective for addressing specific soil-related challenges. It explores challenges such as maintaining soil organic carbon (SOC), controlling erosion, managing nutrients, and other challenges. Farmers are asked to assess the relevance of various practices, including crop rotation, cover cropping, no-till farming, agroforestry, and other practices, in promoting soil health. This information aids in identifying which practices are valued for soil conservation and improvement, providing a basis for recommendations on sustainable soil management practices across different environmental contexts. The responses were collected through a multiple-choice format to capture a range of perspectives on effective soil management strategies.

In each section, there was an option for farmers to share additional information. This open-ended section allows participants to provide further insights, suggestions, or feedback, enabling them to express views or observations not addressed in the preceding questions. This format captures valuable qualitative data and ensures that relevant information outside the structured questions is included, thereby enhancing the depth of the questionnaire's findings.

2.2. Data collection

The target population for the questionnaire included farmers from various agricultural regions within the participating countries. Representatives from each country were assigned the responsibility of disseminating and collecting 30 completed questionnaires. The questionnaire was administered online using the Google Forms platform and, in some cases, in person, with farmers contacted through agricultural associations, cooperatives, and extension services within each country. Participation in the questionnaire is voluntary, and all respondents were assured of the confidentiality of their data. Personal information, such as the farmer's name, is optional, and responses were anonymized for analysis.

2.3. Data analysis

All questionnaire responses were compiled into an Excel spreadsheet for subsequent analysis. To facilitate data interpretation, graphical representations were created to illustrate the results. In the report, data are presented in two formats: as absolute counts of responses and as percentages, both overall and disaggregated by country. Results are described based on the aggregate responses of all participants as well as by individual countries. However, due to variability in response data, the results may not fully represent each country as intended. Additional responses may be required to enhance the comparability and robustness of findings across countries.

The results of the evaluation of agroecological practices and their effectiveness in addressing soil-related challenges were interpreted with the support of a literature review. This analysis helped

to contextualize the findings and provided a deeper understanding of how these practices can enhance soil health and sustainability in agricultural systems.

3. Results

3.1. Section 1: Demographic Information

3.1.1. Personal Information

Age

The age structure data reveals that out of a total of 151 individuals, 21% are under 35, 61% are aged 35-64, and 19% are over 65 (Figure 3.1.1). The significant representation of middle-aged adults indicates a stable workforce with valuable experience, while the low proportion of younger individuals suggests a potential challenge in attracting and retaining new entrants. Additionally, the presence of older adults highlights the need for succession planning and knowledge transfer strategies.

Figure 3.1.1 Age distribution of respondents (n=151)

Gender

The gender distribution within the questionnaire indicates a significant imbalance, with 25% of respondents identifying as female and 75% as male (Figure 3.1.2). This disparity highlights a predominantly male demographic in the dataset, which may reflect broader trends within the agricultural sector.

Figure 3.1.2 Gender distribution of respondents (n=151)

Education level

The educational background of respondents (Figure 3.1.3) shows a varied distribution, with the largest proportion having completed university education: 24% hold a Bachelor's degree, 23% have a Master's degree, and 7% have a PhD. 22% of respondents completed high school, and 19% have only primary education. A small portion (5%) reported other forms of education. This diverse educational landscape highlights a range of knowledge levels among participants, with a strong presence of university-educated individuals, which may influence their approach to agricultural practices and innovation.

Figure 3.1.3 Education level distribution of respondents (n=151)

Participation in farming-related courses

(Answer to “Have you attended any farming-related courses?”)

In the questionnaire, 53% of respondents reported having attended farming-related courses, while 47% had not (Figure 3.1.4). This suggests that a slight majority of participants have engaged in additional education or training related to farming, which could impact their adoption of new practices and overall farm management strategies.

Figure 3.1.4 Attendance of farming-related courses (n=151)

Respondents who attended farming-related courses specified a range of topics and formats, often emphasizing practical and region-specific agricultural practices. Key areas included **soil management**, with workshops focused on soil health and sustainable practices; **plant and crop production**, covering integrated crop protection, vegetable growing, and medicinal plant cultivation; and **livestock management**, which included topics such as animal welfare and feed preparation. Many participants also engaged in courses on **organic and regenerative farming**, particularly in biological farming, as well as training on **irrigation and energy efficiency**, focusing on efficient irrigation methods and farm energy management. Additionally, respondents highlighted their participation in courses related to **agricultural economics and policy**, including farm economics, CAP policy, and subsidy systems. Additionally, other educational workshops and seminars were mentioned. Respondents highlighted a variety of farming-related courses, indicating that farmers are actively seeking education and showing a willingness to adopt new practices.

In general, respondents attended these courses regularly, especially during the offseason. The courses were organized by various institutions, including **agricultural advisory centres**, which provided workshops on sustainable practices; **ministries of agriculture** that conducted periodic sessions; and **local agricultural cooperatives** that offered training on farming techniques and crop management. **Higher education institutions**, such as universities and research institutes, organized seminars and specialized courses on advanced farming methods. Some courses were delivered by **private companies** selling agricultural inputs, focusing on training related to their products and technologies. Additionally, **consulting agencies** offered updates on best practices and policy changes, while **non-governmental organizations (NGOs)** provided workshops on organic farming and sustainable agriculture. Therefore, it can be concluded that these institutions play a crucial role in providing continuous education to farmers and keeping them updated on evolving agricultural practices and regulations.

Years of farming experience

The farming experience of the respondents is distributed across various ranges, showing a diverse level of expertise (Figure 3.1.5). Most farmers have substantial experience, with 30% of respondents having over 30 years of farming experience, representing the most experienced group. Another significant portion, 26% of respondents, have between 20-30 years of experience. Those with 10-20 years of experience make up 19% of respondents, while 13% of respondents have between 5-10 years of experience. Lastly, 13% of respondents are relatively new to farming, with less than 5

years of experience. This distribution reflects a balanced representation of both experienced and newer farmers, indicating a diverse array of knowledge and skills within the farming community.

Figure 3.1.5 Distribution of years of farming experience among respondents (n=151)

Country

During the questionnaire, responses were received from seven countries (Figure 3.1.6). The distribution of respondents was as follows: 20% from Latvia, 20% from Lithuania, and 20% from Turkey. Poland accounted for 15% with 22 responses, while Czechia and Italy each represented 9% of the responses. Spain had the lowest representation at 7% of the responses. Response rates varied across countries, indicating differing levels of engagement. Latvia, Lithuania, and Turkey each contributed 30 responses, while Spain had the fewest, potentially impacting the representativeness of findings across regions.

Figure 3.1.6 Distribution of respondents by country (n=151)

Environmental zone

The questionnaire encompassed respondents from various environmental zones across Europe (Figure 3.1.7), classified according to the categories defined by Metzger et al. (2005). Specifically, Latvia and Lithuania are situated in the **Nemoral (NEM) zone**, contributing 40% of the responses. Poland and Czechia fall within the **Continental (CON) zone**, accounting for 24% of the collected responses. Spain, Turkey, and Italy are primarily located in the **Mediterranean South (MDS) zone**, from which 30% of the responses were gathered. Additionally, Italy provided responses from other environmental zones, including the **Alpine South (ALS) zone**, with 2 responses; the **Mediterranean**

Mountains (MDM) zone, with 1 response; and the **Mediterranean North (MDN) zone**, with 7 responses. This diverse representation across different environmental zones enables a comprehensive understanding of the regional perspectives and challenges related to sustainable soil management and agroecological practices.

Figure 3.1.7 Distribution of respondents by environmental zone (n=151)

3.1.2. Farm Information

Farm size

The bar chart categorizes farm sizes (Figure 3.1.8), ranging from less than 2 hectares to more than 100 hectares. Farms <2 ha represent the least common size group, comprising only 3% of the total count. Farms 2-4.9 ha show a more significant presence, accounting for 12% of the total. Farms 5-9.9 ha represent 7% of the total count. Farms 10-19.9 ha account for 15% of the total count. Farms 20-29.9 ha account for 9% of the total. Farms 30-49.9 ha represent 10% of the total count. Farms 50-99.9 ha make up 12% of the total. Finally, farms >100 ha dominate the dataset, comprising 33% of the total. This distribution illustrates a clear trend towards larger farm sizes, emphasizing the increasing consolidation within the agricultural sector. While large farms are strongly represented, mid-sized and small farms also contribute to a diverse farming landscape. The variation in farm sizes reflects different operational capacities, resource access, and market strategies within the agricultural sector.

Figure 3.1.8 Distribution of farm size (n=151)

Farm size by country

Farm size by country illustrates the variations in land holdings across countries (Figure 3.1.9). **Czechia** exhibits a 71% predominance of large farms (>100 ha), reflecting a strong trend towards extensive agricultural practices. 29 % of farms fall within the 20-29.9 ha, 30-49.9 ha, and 50-99.9 ha categories, indicating limited representation of small and medium-sized farms. The farm size distribution in **Italy** is more balanced, with 29% of farms in the 10-19.9 ha category and 14% in the 2-4.9 ha, 30-49.9 ha, 50-99.9 ha, and >100 ha categories. This suggests a diverse agricultural landscape that includes a mix of small to medium-sized operations alongside larger farms. **Latvia** shows a significant concentration of larger farms, 67% exceeding 100 ha. Additionally, 17% of farms fall within the 20-29.9 ha category. This suggests a significant trend towards larger-scale farming practices in the country. **Lithuania** displays a notable presence of large farms, with 27% of farms exceeding 100 ha. The 20% representation in the 2-4.9 ha and 10-19.9 ha categories also highlights the existence of smaller farms, indicating a diverse agricultural framework. In **Poland**, 64% of farms are categorized as either 50-99.9 ha or >100 ha, while 36% fall within the 20-29.9 ha and 30-49.9 ha categories. This distribution indicates a trend towards medium to large farming operations, with limited representation in the smaller farm size categories. **Spain's** farm size distribution is characterized by a moderate presence of small farms, with 18% of farms falling into the <2 ha, 5-9.9 ha, 10-19.9 ha, 20-29.9 ha, 30-49.9 ha, and >100 ha categories. Similarly, as in Italy distribution shows a combination of small and large agricultural holdings, highlighting the country's diverse

agricultural landscape. However, the limited number of collected questionnaires may impact the analysis and affect the results' representativeness. **Turkey** has a remarkable proportion of small and medium farms, with 73% of farms categorized in the 2-4.9 ha, 5-9.9 ha, and 10-19.9 ha categories. The significant presence of small farms reflects a predominantly smallholder farming system, which may suggest challenges related to economies of scale.

Figure 3.1.9 Distribution of farm size by country (n=151)

The farm size distribution across these countries highlights diverse agricultural landscapes. Countries like **Czechia, Poland, Latvia, and Lithuania** show a tendency toward larger farms, while **Turkey** showcases a strong prevalence of smaller holdings.

Agricultural area utilization

Agricultural land use practices are divided into several categories (Figure 3.1.10), with arable land comprising the largest share at 48%. Permanent grassland accounts for 22%, supporting grazing and other perennial plant growth. Permanent crops represent 15% of the total agricultural area. Smaller portions include kitchen gardens at 11%, dedicated to household-level food production. A minor portion, 4%, of agricultural land remains unutilized. This distribution highlights a strong focus on arable land for intensive cropping, balanced with significant areas for grazing and permanent crops.

Figure 3.1.10 Distribution of agricultural area utilization types

The distribution of agricultural area utilization types by country reveals varying proportions (Figure 3.1.11). **Czechia** dedicates 42% of its agricultural area to arable land and 42% to permanent

grassland, indicating a balanced approach between crop production and livestock farming. It allocates 17% to permanent crops and focuses on crop diversity and efficient land management. **Italy** shows a diverse agricultural profile with 55% of land used for arable farming and 30% for permanent crops, reflecting its strength in fruit and tree cultivation. Kitchen gardens account for 10%, while permanent grassland is minimal at 5%. **Latvia** utilizes 42% for arable land and 25% for permanent grassland, indicating a balance between crop and livestock production. Permanent crops comprise 15%, with 12% dedicated to kitchen gardens. There is 7% unutilized agricultural land, particularly as some areas are undergoing ecological succession, leading to overgrowth by trees. **Lithuania** allocates 51% to arable farming and 31% to permanent grassland. Permanent crops are low at 2%, while kitchen gardens make up 10%. The country has 6% unutilized land, suggesting a trend of land abandonment, which is also observed in Latvia, where similar ecological succession occurs. **Poland** has 38% of its agricultural area for arable land and 26% for permanent grassland. It also has the highest percentage of kitchen gardens at 21%. Permanent crops account for 10%, with 5% of unutilized land available. **Spain** utilizes only 14% of its agricultural land for arable farming, the lowest among the countries studied, and has no permanent grassland. Instead, it focuses more on permanent crops, which account for 10%, and 7% of unutilized agricultural land. **Turkey** stands out with 86% of its agricultural area devoted to arable land, emphasizing crop production. It has 0% for permanent grassland and 9% for permanent crops, with 6% of land allocated to kitchen gardens and no unutilized agricultural area.

Figure 3.1.11 Distribution of agricultural area utilization types by country

This highlights distinct agricultural practices across countries. Poland, Czechia, Latvia, and Lithuania show reliance on permanent grassland and arable land, indicating traditional farming practices. Spain places a strong emphasis on permanent crops, indicating a shift towards the production of fruits and vegetables. Turkey shows many entries for arable land, including greenhouses, indicating a diverse approach to crop production.

Livestock presence

(if applicable)

In a questionnaire, 66% of farmers reported no livestock presence, while 34% included livestock in their farming practices (Figure 3.1.12). This indicates a predominant reliance on crop production, suggesting that most farms focus on specialized agricultural practices rather than mixed farming.

Figure 3.1.12 Livestock presence (n=151)

The data reveals that cattle are the most prevalent livestock type, comprising **57%** of total livestock across the surveyed countries, followed by sheep at **15%**, pigs at **12%**, poultry at **7%**, and goats at **6%**. Horses were also mentioned in the dataset (Figure 3.1.13).

Figure 3.1.13 Distribution of livestock presence

Czechia accounts for 58% of livestock in cattle, indicating beef and dairy production. Sheep represent 16%, while pigs make up 11%. **Latvia** has cattle comprising 50% of livestock, with 17% for pigs and 11% for sheep. **Lithuania** has cattle making up 45% of livestock, with a significant representation of pigs, goats, and poultry, each at 18%. **Poland** has cattle accounting for 67%, while poultry and pigs make up 17%. **Turkey** demonstrates 50% cattle, with 42% of livestock being sheep, reflecting traditional smallholder practices. **Italy** and **Spain** predominantly exhibit no livestock presence (Figure 3.1.14).

In summary, cattle dominate livestock populations across most countries, especially in Czechia, Poland, and Turkey. Latvia and Lithuania also show significant cattle representation, while Poland maintains a diverse agricultural system with notable pig and poultry numbers. Turkey’s livestock distribution highlights traditional smallholder practices with a considerable sheep presence. In contrast, Italy and Spain exhibit minimal livestock presence, suggesting reliance on alternative agricultural practices.

Figure 3.1.14 Distribution of livestock presence by country

3.2. Section 2: Ecological Identity

3.2.1. Perception of Agroecological Practices

Familiarity with agroecological practices

(Answer to “How familiar are you with the definition of agroecological practices?”)

The survey results regarding familiarity with agroecological practices (Figure 3.2.1) indicate that 13% of respondents reported being not familiar at all with the definition. A larger group, comprising 56% of respondents, stated they are somewhat familiar with the concept. Additionally, 31% of respondents indicated that they are very familiar with agroecological practices. While the majority express at least some familiarity with agroecology, a notable portion remain either unaware or only slightly informed.

Figure 3.2.1 Familiarity with agroecological practices (n=151)

The data on familiarity with agroecological practices reveals varying levels of awareness across countries (Figure 3.2.2). In **Czechia**, 64% are somewhat familiar, 29% are very familiar, and 7% are not familiar. **Italy** shows equal familiarity, with 50% somewhat and 50% very familiar. **Latvia** has 57% somewhat familiar, 37% very familiar, and 7% not familiar. In **Lithuania**, 50% are somewhat familiar, 40% very familiar, and 10% not familiar. **Poland** shows 55% somewhat familiar, 27% very familiar, and 18% not familiar. **Spain** has the highest awareness, with 64% very familiar and only 9% not familiar. **Turkey** lags, with 73% somewhat familiar and 27% not familiar at all, and no one very familiar. In summary, while awareness is generally widespread, Spain shows the highest familiarity, while Turkey shows the least.

Figure 3.2.2 Familiarity with agroecological practices by country (n=151)

Farmer evaluations on the importance of agroecological practices in modern farming

(Answer to “Evaluate the significance of agroecological practices in modern farming”)

The evaluation of the significance of agroecological practices in modern farming reveals a strong positive perception among respondents (Figure 3.2.3). Specifically, 27% of respondents categorized these practices as extremely important, while 41% of respondents regarded them as very important. Furthermore, 21% of respondents deemed agroecological practices moderately important. Conversely, a smaller group, consisting of 5% of respondents, considered them somewhat important, and 6% viewed them as not important. These results suggest a robust recognition of agroecological practices' significance in enhancing sustainability and resilience in modern agricultural systems.

Figure 3.2.3 Farmer evaluations on the importance of agroecological practices in modern farming (n=151)

The evaluation of the significance of agroecological practices in modern farming varies among the surveyed countries (Figure 3.2.4). **Czechia** shows strong support, with 29% rating them as extremely important and 43% as very important, resulting in a total of 72% considering them at least very important. Notably, no respondents rated them as unimportant. **Italy** also reflects a high level of importance, with 36% deeming them extremely important and 43% as very important. However, 7% of respondents find them not important, indicating a slight divergence in perception. In **Latvia**, a significant 57% rate agroecological practices as very important, while 20% consider them extremely important, showcasing strong acknowledgment of their relevance. Remarkably, no respondents rated them as not important. **Lithuania** has the highest percentage of respondents (40%) identifying agroecological practices as extremely important. However, 30% consider them very important, and 7% find them somewhat important. **Poland** presents a balanced perspective, with 23% considering them extremely important and 45% as very important. A notable 27% rate them as moderately important, while no respondents find them unimportant. In **Spain**, the perception is somewhat mixed; 27% deem them extremely important, and 36% as moderately important. The 9% who find them not important indicate a lack of consensus. **Turkey** shows a varied perspective, with 20% rating agroecological practices as extremely important and 37% as very important. However, 23% consider them not important, highlighting a significant level of scepticism among some respondents.

The data indicates a generally positive perception of agroecological practices across these countries, with a majority viewing them as important for modern farming. However, the presence of not important ratings in Italy, Spain, and Turkey suggests that some farmers may be less convinced of their relevance or may have other priorities in agricultural practices.

Figure 3.2.4 Farmer evaluations on the importance of agroecological practices in modern farming by country (n=151)

Farmer perspectives on agroecological practices

(Answers to “Which practices from the list below would you consider to be agroecological?”)

Farmers' responses indicate a mix of understanding regarding agroecological practices (Figure 3.2.5). Many practices align well with agroecological principles, though some conventional methods are mistakenly identified as agroecological. Key agroecological practices that were widely recognized include crop rotation, which garnered support from 85% of respondents, and legume crops, acknowledged by 59%. Intercropping and multiple cropping received recognition from 52% of participants, while cover and catch crops were identified by 55%. Rotational grazing also gained acknowledgement at 40%. These practices collectively promote biodiversity, enhance soil fertility, and encourage sustainable resource use. Soil conservation practices, such as no-till farming, were correctly identified by 44% of respondents as agroecological. In the area of nutrient management, appropriate compost application was recognized by 45% of farmers, and manure application received support from 60%, highlighting their roles in nutrient cycling and organic matter retention. Organic farming was acknowledged by 53% of participants, and agroforestry was recognized by 40%, both of which emphasize ecological balance and sustainability. Additionally, agroecological farming received strong recognition from 58% of respondents, as it closely aligns with agroecological principles by integrating ecological processes into farming systems. The incorporation of crop residues was understood by 57% of farmers as a practice that enhances soil organic matter and promotes nutrient recycling. However, precision agriculture, although improving resource efficiency through technology, was also recognized by 58% of respondents but is not inherently agroecological. It often relies on conventional inputs like synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, which agroecology seeks to minimize. This distinction highlights the need for further education to differentiate between ecological sustainability and technological efficiency. Moreover, some conventional practices were incorrectly perceived as agroecological. Deep ploughing, recognized by 33% of participants, disrupts soil structure, while precision herbicide application was acknowledged by 47% of respondents, even though it still relies on chemicals. Additionally, reduced mineral fertilizer use, which was seen as agroecological by 60% of respondents, remains reliant on synthetic inputs that agroecology aims to minimize.

While farmers have a solid understanding of many core agroecological practices, further education is needed to clarify the environmental impacts of conventional methods like deep ploughing, herbicide use, and synthetic fertilizers.

Figure 3.2.5 Farmer perspectives on agroecological practices (number represents vote count)

3.2.2. Current Farming Practices

Farmers current farming practices

(Answer to “Select the practices that are relevant for your farm”)

This report summarizes the responses from farmers regarding their current farming practices, highlighting which practices they consider relevant for their farms (Figure 3.2.6). This analysis combines both agroecological and conventional approaches. Crop rotation is the most widely adopted practice, with 60% of respondents indicating its use. More cereals are cultivated by 30% of respondents, focusing on high-demand cash crops, although this emphasis may limit biodiversity. The adoption of legume crops is notable at 29%, as these crops contribute to nitrogen fixation and improve soil fertility. Intercropping/multiple cropping, practised by 18%, are less common despite their benefits for soil conservation and biodiversity. The adoption of cover and catch crops is relatively low at 19%, while perennial crops are utilized by 23% of respondents. This suggests that these agronomically beneficial practices have not yet reached widespread implementation within the agricultural sector.

In livestock management, the adoption of permanent grazing is low at 5%, and zero grazing is even rarer at 3%. Rotational grazing, however, is utilized by 13% of respondents. In terms of soil management and tillage, no-till practices remain low at 11%, while non-inversion and reduced tillage are practised by 24%, reflecting a shift toward reduced soil disturbance. Deep ploughing continues to dominate at 39%, suggesting that conventional tillage methods still prevail despite growing environmental concerns. Fertilization planning is common among 40% of respondents, indicating a move toward data-driven approaches. Reduced or more precise mineral fertilizer application is practised by 26%. Incorporation of crop residues is widely adopted at 38%, but appropriate compost application is less common at 15%, and biochar application is utilized by only 1%. Better manure storage is reported by 13% of respondents, while manure treatment is even lower at 9%. Mechanical weeding is relatively low at 16% compared to precision herbicide application, which is reported by 28% of respondents. Regarding farming systems, organic farming is practised by 19%, while agroecological farming is less common at 12%. Precision agriculture is utilized by 13%, but practices such as agroforestry and conservation agriculture remain underutilized, with adoption rates of only 3% and 5%, respectively.

This analysis highlights a growing interest in sustainable agriculture, with practices like crop rotation and precision nutrient management becoming more common. However, conventional methods such as deep ploughing and precision herbicide application remain widespread. Organic farming and reduced tillage are moderately adopted, reflecting some shift toward sustainability. Yet, agroforestry, no-till farming, and conservation agriculture are still underutilized. Overall, while progress is being made, traditional farming practices continue to dominate, signalling the need for more education, incentives, and support to boost the adoption of agroecological approaches.

Figure 3.2.6 Farmers current farming practices (number represents vote count)

Assessment of environmental friendliness in farming practices

(Answer to “To what extent do you consider your farming practices to be environmentally friendly?”)

Survey results show varied perceptions of environmental sustainability in farming practices (Figure 3.2.7). The assessment of farming practices reveals that 23% of respondents consider their methods very environmentally friendly, indicating a commitment to sustainability. 39% categorize their practices as moderately environmentally friendly, suggesting some adoption of sustainable techniques. In contrast, 28% view their methods as somewhat environmentally friendly, indicating a mixed approach, while 9% identify their practices as not environmentally friendly. This distribution highlights that while many farmers are embracing environmentally friendly practices, there remains significant potential for enhancing sustainability in agriculture.

Figure 3.2.7 Assessment of environmental friendliness in farming practices (n=151)

The evaluation of environmental friendliness in farming practices varies significantly across countries (Figure 3.2.8). In **Czechia**, 21% of farmers view their practices as very environmentally friendly, while 50% consider them moderately environmentally friendly, and 29% rate them as somewhat environmentally friendly. **Italy** shows a strong commitment, with 50% of respondents stating their practices are very environmentally friendly, although 7% perceive them as not environmentally friendly. **Latvia** reports that 43% of farmers consider their methods very environmentally friendly and 47% moderately environmentally friendly. In **Lithuania**, 10% consider their practices very environmentally friendly, with 57% rating them as moderately environmentally friendly. **Poland** reveals a more varied perspective, with only 18% viewing their practices as very environmentally friendly, while 45% classify them as somewhat environmentally friendly. **Spain** shows a mixed assessment, with 27% of farmers stating their practices are very environmentally friendly, and 55% indicating they are somewhat environmentally friendly. In **Turkey**, only 7% of farmers consider their practices very environmentally friendly, while 33% feel their methods are not environmentally friendly. Results suggest that while there is a notable commitment to environmental friendliness in some countries, significant differences exist, highlighting areas for improvement and further education on sustainable practices.

Figure 3.2.8 Assessment of environmental friendliness in farming practices by country (n=151)

3.3. Section 3: Awareness of Agroecological Practices

3.3.1. Knowledge Level

Knowledge levels with agroecological practices among farmers

Farmers were asked to evaluate their familiarity with a range of agroecological practices on a scale from 1 ("Never heard of it") to 5 ("Implement this practice"). The results indicate varying levels of awareness and adoption across the practices, reflecting both the diversity of knowledge within the farming community and the extent to which different practices are used in daily farming practices, as well as analysis reveals significant differences among countries.

Crop rotation is one of the most widely known and implemented practices (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(a)), with 48% of farmers actively using it and 24% moderately familiar with it. Only 5% of farmers have never heard of crop rotation, indicating that it is a well-established technique. The analysis of crop rotation practices reveals significant disparities among countries. In **Czechia**, 57% of farmers actively implement crop rotation, while **Italy** leads with 82%. **Latvia** also shows strong adoption at 72%, and **Lithuania** has 50% of farmers practising it. Conversely, **Poland** has 50% moderately familiar with the practice but only 14% actively implementing it. **Spain** reports no active implementation despite 45% familiarity, while **Turkey** shows 47% engagement but 17% have never heard of it.

On the other hand, **polyculture** remains less familiar (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(b)), with 37% of farmers unaware of it and only 6% of farmers implementing it, although 31% of farmers have some familiarity. In **Czechia**, 36% of farmers have never heard of it, with only 7% actively implementing the practice. **Italy** shows a balanced approach, with 50% of farmers implementing crop rotation, while 50% are moderately familiar. **Latvia** has 44% unaware of the practice, with 11% implementing it. **Lithuania** has a high familiarity rate at 62%, yet no active implementation. **Poland** exhibits a similar trend, with no farmers actively using it. **Spain** and **Turkey** show considerable gaps in awareness, with 55% and 70% of farmers, respectively, having never heard of polyculture.

The **intercropping** data (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(c)) shows that 23% of farmers have never heard of the practice, and 20% are not familiar with it. While 26% are somewhat familiar and 23% are moderately familiar, only 9% actively implement intercropping. In **Czechia**, 29% have never heard of it, and 7% actively implement the practice. **Italy** stands out with 45% of farmers implementing intercropping, while only 9% are unfamiliar. In **Latvia**, 36% are not familiar, and 7% implement it. **Lithuania** shows 50% moderately familiar, with 13% implementing. **Poland** has 41% who are not familiar and 5% who implement it. In **Spain**, 36% have never heard of intercropping. Lastly, **Turkey** has 60% unfamiliar and only 3% implementing.

Companion planting is another practice with lower levels of awareness (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(d)), as 33% had never heard of it. Only 29% are somewhat familiar, and just 4% actively implement the practice. **Czechia** reports 57% of respondents had never heard of the practice, while **Turkey** shows the highest at 73%. In contrast, **Italy** demonstrates a more balanced understanding, with 50% being moderately familiar and 13% implementing the practice. **Lithuania** has the highest percentage of somewhat familiar respondents at 53%, while **Poland** shows moderate levels of awareness, with 41% reporting they have heard of it but are not familiar, while **Spain** reflects a higher percentage of 36% who have never heard of companion planting or somewhat familiar. **Latvia** shows that 21% have never heard of companion planting, with 29% indicating they are somewhat familiar.

Awareness of **agroforestry** practices is low (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(e)), with 39% of farmers reporting they have never heard of it. Additionally, 26% have heard of it but are not familiar, and 25% are somewhat familiar. Only 8% consider themselves moderately familiar, while just 3% actively implement this practice. **Turkey** shows the lowest familiarity, with 93% of farmers indicating they have never heard of it. **Spain** follows closely, with 40% of respondents also unaware of agroforestry. In **Poland**, 59% have heard of it but are not familiar, while **Czechia** and **Lithuania** report 29% of farmers as somewhat familiar. **Italy** has balanced awareness across categories, with

22% of respondents in each category, including those who implement the practice. **Latvia** has 33% who are somewhat familiar and 30% who have never heard of agroforestry.

Awareness of **cover cropping** among farmers shows a significant knowledge gap (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(f)), with 24.5% having never heard of it and 15.4% not familiar despite having heard of it. In contrast, 25.9% are somewhat familiar and 23.1% are moderately familiar. However, only 11.2% actively implement cover cropping. In **Czechia**, 21% of farmers implement it, while 29% have heard of it but are not familiar. **Italy** shows 30% implementation, with 40% moderately familiar. **Latvia** has 38% somewhat familiar but only 8% implementing. **Lithuania** has 23% implementing and 37% moderately familiar. In **Poland**, 55% are somewhat familiar, but only 5% actively practice it. **Spain** has no implementation, while **Turkey** has 80% who have never heard of it.

Awareness of **perennial cropping** among farmers reveals a varied understanding (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(g)), with 16.9% having never heard of it and 9.9% unfamiliar despite some awareness. On the positive side, 23.9% of farmers are somewhat familiar, and 24.7% are moderately familiar, with an additional 24.7% actively implementing the practice. In **Czechia**, 28.6% implement perennial cropping, while 28.6% have heard of it but remain unfamiliar. **Italy** shows a stronger implementation rate at 37.5%, with 25% moderately familiar. In **Latvia**, 37% implement it, with 40.7% moderately familiar. **Lithuania** reports 23.3% implementation, while 43.3% are somewhat familiar. In **Poland**, 22.7% implement perennial cropping, with a notable 36.4% somewhat familiar. In **Spain**, 81.8% have never heard of it, leading to minimal engagement. Meanwhile, **Turkey** has 33.3% unaware of the practice, while 16.7% implement it.

Awareness of **permaculture** among farmers is low (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(h)), with 37% having never heard of it. 27% are aware but not familiar, and 26% are somewhat familiar. Only 8% are moderately familiar, while just 2% actively implement permaculture practices. In **Czechia**, 21% have never heard of it, while 43% are aware but not familiar. In **Italy**, 38% are unaware, and 25% actively implement it. **Latvia** shows 11% with no knowledge, but 41% are somewhat familiar. In **Lithuania**, 23% have never heard of permaculture, and 37% are somewhat familiar. **Poland** has 50% unaware and 14% somewhat familiar. In **Spain**, 27% are unaware, with 36% being somewhat familiar. Lastly, **Turkey** shows the highest lack of awareness, with 73% having never heard of it.

Awareness of **rotational grazing** among farmers is mixed (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(i)). 28% have never heard of it, while 20% are aware but not familiar. 30% report being somewhat familiar, and 13% consider themselves moderately familiar. Only 9% actively implement rotational grazing practices. In **Czechia**, 7% have never heard of it, while 21% are not familiar. In **Italy**, 22% report they have never heard of it, but 44% are somewhat familiar. **Latvia** shows a different trend, with 16% never having heard of it and 28% actively implementing the practice. In **Lithuania**, 23% are unaware, and 3% implement it. **Poland** has 9% unaware and 14% practicing it. **Spain** sees 18% unaware and 55% somewhat familiar. Lastly, **Turkey** has a high 70% who have never heard of rotational grazing, with only 3% implementing it.

Awareness of **livestock integration** is relatively low (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(j)), with 33% of respondents having never heard of it. 17% are aware but not familiar, while 28% are somewhat familiar. 14% report being moderately familiar, and only 7% actively implement livestock integration in their farming practices. **Turkey** shows the lowest familiarity, with 87% having never heard of it, while **Italy** has the highest implementation at 33%. **Latvia** also has low awareness, with 36% having never heard of the practice. **Spain** demonstrates high awareness, with 64% somewhat familiar. **Czechia** and **Lithuania** also show moderate levels of familiarity, with 14% in Czechia and 10% in Lithuania actively implementing the practice.

Awareness of **agroecological farming** practices is varied (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(k)). Around 27% of respondents have never heard of it, while 22% have heard of it but are not familiar. 26% are somewhat familiar, and 17% moderately familiar. Only 8% of respondents actively implement agroecological farming practices. In **Czechia**, 36% have never heard of it, compared to 67% in **Turkey**. **Italy** shows strong familiarity, with 56% moderately familiar and 33% implementing it. **Latvia** and **Lithuania** have notable levels of awareness, with 39% and 30% somewhat familiar,

respectively. Meanwhile, **Spain** has the highest rate of implementation at 36%, while **Poland** has not actively used agroecological practices.

Awareness and implementation of **organic farming** practices are relatively widespread (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(l)). Only 8% have never heard of it, while 18% actively implement organic farming. 27% are somewhat familiar, and 26% are moderately familiar, indicating that a significant portion of farmers are knowledgeable but not yet fully engaged in organic methods. In **Czechia**, 29% of farmers implement it, while **Italy** has the highest rate at 50%. **Latvia** also shows strong engagement, with 36% practising organic farming. Conversely, in **Poland**, only 9% are unfamiliar with it, but none actively practice it. **Turkey** shows the highest percentage of unfamiliarity at 20%, while **Spain** and **Lithuania** have moderate levels of implementation.

No-till farming shows a diverse range of awareness and implementation among farmers (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(m)). Overall, 15% have never heard of it, while 33% are moderately familiar, and 10% actively implement the practice. In **Czechia**, 8% have never heard of no-till farming, and 8% implement it, while 46% are unfamiliar. **Italy** reports no farmers unaware of the practice, with 22% somewhat familiar, 44% moderately familiar, and 33% implementing it. **Latvia** shows 32% somewhat familiar, 57% moderately familiar, and 11% implementing. **Lithuania** reports 48% somewhat familiar, while **Poland** has 50% somewhat familiar. **Spain** has 36% somewhat familiar and 27% implementing it. **Turkey** has a significant 60% unaware of no-till farming.

Awareness of **biological nitrogen fixation** varied among farmers (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(n)). 25% have never heard of the practice, while only 4% are aware but not familiar. 25% report being somewhat familiar, and 30% are moderately familiar with it. Notably, 16% actively implement biological nitrogen fixation practices. In **Czechia**, 23% of farmers have never heard of it, while 23% implement the practice. **Italy** reports no unfamiliarity, with 44% somewhat familiar, 33% moderately familiar, and 22% implementing it. In **Latvia**, 11% are somewhat familiar, 46% moderately familiar, and 43% implement it. **Lithuania** has 45% somewhat familiar, but only 3% implement the practice. **Poland** shows 55% somewhat familiar and 14% implementing, while **Spain** has 27% unaware, 9% somewhat familiar, and 9% implementing. **Turkey** shows a high unawareness rate at 97%, with only 3% implementing the practice.

Awareness of **soil conservation techniques** among farmers is relatively varied (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(o)). 18% have never heard of these techniques, while 18% are aware but not familiar. A notable 37% are somewhat familiar, 18% are moderately familiar, and 9% actively implement these practices. In **Czechia**, 14% have never heard of these techniques, with 36% unaware but familiar, and 14% actively implementing them. **Italy** shows strong implementation at 63%, while 38% are moderately familiar. In **Latvia**, 15% have never heard of them, 41% are somewhat familiar, but none implement the techniques. **Lithuania** has 60% somewhat familiar, and 3% implementing. **Poland** shows 64% somewhat familiar but no implementation. In **Spain**, 45% implement soil conservation techniques, while 36% are moderately familiar. Finally, **Turkey** has 53% never heard of these techniques, with no implementation reported.

Awareness of **water management techniques** among farmers is relatively mixed (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(p)). 8% have never heard of these techniques, while 22% are aware but not familiar. 31% report being somewhat familiar, and 17% are moderately familiar. A significant 22% actively implement water management practices. In **Czechia**, 7% of farmers are unaware of water management techniques, while 50% are unfamiliar, and 7% implement them. In **Italy**, 44% implement these techniques, with another 44% moderately familiar. **Latvia** shows 11% unaware, 25% unfamiliar, and 21% implementing. **Lithuania** has 7% unaware, 30% unfamiliar, 47% somewhat familiar, and 7% implementing. **Poland** reports 32% unfamiliar and 50% somewhat familiar, with no implementation. **Spain** has 9% unaware, 9% unfamiliar, and 73% implementing. **Turkey** indicates 17% unaware, 20% somewhat familiar, 23% moderately familiar, and 37% implementing.

Farmers show varied awareness of **organic matter and nutrient management** (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(q)). Approximately 10% have never heard of it, while 9% are aware but not familiar. A

significant 31% report being somewhat familiar, and 25% consider themselves moderately familiar. Notably, 25% actively implement this practice. In **Czechia**, 29% have never heard of it, and 29% actively implement it. In **Italy**, 50% implement the practice, while 40% are moderately familiar. **Latvia** shows 38% implementing it, with 34% moderately familiar. In **Lithuania**, 30% implement the practice, and 40% are somewhat familiar. In **Poland**, 68% are somewhat familiar, but only 5% implement it. In **Spain**, 64% are moderately familiar, and 18% implement it. **Turkey** has 43% never heard of it, with 17% implementing it.

Awareness of **integrated pest management** varies across countries (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(r)). Overall, 18% have never heard of it, and 13% are unfamiliar. A significant 32% report being somewhat familiar, while 27% are moderately familiar. Only 8% actively implement integrated pest management practices. In **Czechia**, 7% have never heard of it, with 43% unfamiliar and 14% implementing it. **Italy** shows no farmers unaware, with 43% somewhat familiar and 29% implementing. **Latvia** reports 7% unaware, 43% somewhat familiar, and 14% implementing. In **Lithuania**, 47% are moderately familiar and 7% implement it. **Poland** has 59% somewhat familiar and 5% implementing. **Spain** shows 18% unaware, 36% somewhat familiar, and 9% implementing. Finally, **Turkey** has 70% unaware, with no implementation reported.

Awareness of **mechanical weeding** varies among farmers (Figure 3.3.1; Appendix 4(s)). The overall awareness shows that 17% have never heard of it, 14% are unfamiliar, 36% are somewhat familiar, 17% are moderately familiar, and 16% actively implement the practice. In **Czechia**, 23% are unfamiliar with the practice. Additionally, 38% consider themselves moderately familiar, and 15% actively implement it. In **Italy**, no farmers are unaware, but 50% are somewhat familiar, and 25% implement mechanical weeding. **Latvia** shows that 14% are unaware, 10% are unfamiliar, and 48% implement the practice. **Lithuania** reports 63% somewhat familiar and only 3% implementing it. In **Poland**, 5% are unaware, 45% are somewhat familiar, and none actively implement it. **Spain** has 9% unaware, with 36% of farmers implementing mechanical weeding. Lastly, **Turkey** has a high rate of unawareness at 59%, with 24% somewhat familiar and none implementing the practice.

The analysis shows that well-established practices like **crop rotation**, **nutrient management**, **perennial crops**, **organic farming** and **no-till farming** are relatively well-known and widely implemented, with over 60% of farmers being at least somewhat familiar with them. In contrast, less conventional practices such as **permaculture**, **polyculture**, and **agroforestry** exhibit lower awareness and adoption, suggesting a need for increased education and resources to promote these practices.

Figure 3.3.1 Evaluation of farmers' knowledge levels of agroecological practices

Information Sources

Farmer training and education on agroecological practices (Answer to “Have you received any training or education on agroecological practices?”)

The questionnaire asked respondents whether they had received any training or education on agroecological practices (Figure 3.3.2). The data reveals that many farmers, 75%, have not received any training or education on agroecological practices, while only 25% have. This significant gap suggests a lack of widespread access to or engagement with educational resources related to sustainable farming methods. The low percentage of trained farmers may hinder the broader adoption of agroecological practices, highlighting the need for targeted training programs and increased support to promote more sustainable agricultural approaches.

Figure 3.3.2 Farmer training and education on agroecological practices (n=151)

The data reveals (Figure 3.3.3) that Poland and Spain lead in agroecological training, with 50% and 45% of farmers receiving education, respectively. Italy follows with 29% of farmers trained. Latvia shows a moderate level of training, with 27% of farmers having received education on agroecological practices. Czechia has 21% of farmers trained, indicating a need for further education efforts in the region. Conversely, Turkey and Lithuania show the lowest levels of agroecological education, with 10% and 13%, respectively, having received training. The data suggests that while some countries show moderate engagement, the majority still lack widespread training.

Figure 3.3.3 Farmer training and education on agroecological practices by country (n=151)

Types of training or workshops attended on agroecological practices (*Answer to “If “Yes”, please specify what kind of training/workshop you attended.”*)

The responses to the question about the types of training or workshops attended regarding agroecological practices reveal a diverse range of experiences among farmers. Many participants engaged in trainings organized by local and national agricultural institutions, including ministries, agricultural chambers, and advisory centres. Common topics covered in these trainings included organic farming, integrated pest management, soil health, and conservation agriculture. Some respondents highlighted their participation in university courses and workshops, while others referred to online resources and bibliographic research. Specific workshops focused on soil health and rational soil cultivation were frequently mentioned, alongside events dedicated to eco-schemes and regenerative agriculture. Additionally, training organized by agricultural cooperatives, chemical companies, and extension services reflects a blend of formal and informal educational experiences. Most of the training received by respondents was practical and closely tied to certification processes or sustainable practices such as organic and regenerative farming. This underscores the practical orientation of current educational efforts in agroecology. However, it is important to note that many farmers have not yet received formal training, as indicated by earlier results.

Sources of information for agroecological training and workshops (*Answer to “If “Yes”, please specify where you found information about training/workshop.”*)

Farmers found information about agroecological training or workshops through a variety of channels. Many respondents indicated that locating such information can be challenging, suggesting potential barriers to accessing training opportunities. Some noted that details were available online through agricultural advisory centres, regional institutions, and universities. Others relied on personal communication, such as phone calls or text messages from colleagues and advisors. Additionally, some individuals followed updates via newsletters or social media related to agricultural organizations. While some resources are accessible online, personal networks and direct communication play a crucial role in disseminating information about available training opportunities.

Sources of information on agricultural practices (*Answer to “Where do you usually seek information about agricultural practices?”*)

Farmers primarily seek information about agricultural practices through a variety of sources (Figure 3.3.4), with a significant emphasis on online resources, which account for 32% of their information-gathering efforts. Agricultural extension services are also highly utilized, comprising 24% of the sources consulted. Conferences and workshops contribute to 22% of the information sought, reflecting the importance of face-to-face learning and networking in the agricultural community. Academic journals and research articles, along with books and publications, are less frequently used, each representing 11% of the sources. While online resources and extension services dominate as preferred channels, there remains a notable interest in experiential learning opportunities such as workshops and conferences. This indicates a multifaceted approach to information-seeking among farmers, balancing both digital and traditional methods.

Figure 3.3.4 Sources of information on agricultural practices

The analysis of sources of information on agricultural practices reveals distinct preferences among farmers across different countries, highlighting regional differences in how agricultural knowledge is accessed (Figure 3.3.5). In **Czechia**, farmers predominantly rely on agricultural extension services at 31%, followed by online resources at 28%. This indicates a strong engagement with institutional support, complemented by a significant use of digital platforms for information. In **Italy**, the reliance on online resources is high at 32%, with a notable emphasis on books and publications at 14%. The use of agricultural extension services is also significant at 25%, suggesting a balanced approach to information sourcing. **Latvia** shows that agricultural extension services are utilized by 19% of farmers, while online resources account for 27%. Additionally, conferences and workshops are a prominent source of information, with 30% of farmers attending these events, indicating a strong interest in interactive learning. In **Lithuania**, the use of online resources is the highest at 42%, underscoring the farmers' preference for digital information. Agricultural extension services are also utilized at 23%. Farmers in **Poland** demonstrate a strong reliance on agricultural extension services at 33%, indicating robust engagement with professional support. Online resources are also significant at 38%. In **Spain**, the use of books and publications stands out at 30%, highlighting a preference for traditional resources. Additionally, online resources are utilized by 22%, with a noteworthy reliance on agricultural extension services, though lower than in other countries. Lastly, in **Turkey**, a notable number of farmers depend on agricultural extension services. Moreover, Turkish farmers emphasize information from experienced farmers, agrochemical and fertilizer dealers, and agricultural engineers or experts.

Figure 3.3.5 Sources of information on agricultural practices by county

Farmers typically seek information about agricultural practices from various sources within their networks and local communities. Many respondents rely on experienced farmers and peers as trusted sources of practical knowledge. Many also consult agrochemical and fertilizer dealers for

advice on products and practices. Additionally, agricultural engineers and experts from local advisory centres or district agriculture directorates are frequently sought for technical guidance. Some farmers mentioned reaching out to colleagues with similar farms or neighbours with larger, more successful operations. Overall, informal networks and local advisors play a crucial role in the decision-making processes of farmers.

This analysis indicates that while online resources and agricultural extension services are prominent across most countries, regional preferences for traditional materials, conferences, and community knowledge reflect the diverse landscape of agricultural information-seeking behaviours among farmers.

3.4. Section 4: Barriers and Facilitators

3.4.1. Barriers to Adoption

Likelihood of future adoption of agroecological practices by farmers

(Answer to “How likely are you to adopt a combination of agroecological practices on your farm in the future?”)

The data reveals that 18% of farmers are not likely to adopt agroecological practices, while 50% are somewhat likely and 32% are very likely to implement them (Figure 3.4.1). These results suggest a generally positive attitude towards agroecological practices, with over 82% of farmers showing potential for adoption more sustainable farming methods.

Figure 3.4.1 Likelihood of future adoption of agroecological practices by farmers (n=151)

The data on the likelihood of adopting agroecological practices across different countries reveals significant variations in farmer attitudes (Figure 3.4.2). In **Czechia**, none of the respondents indicated they are not likely to adopt these practices, with 57% being somewhat likely and 43% very likely to do so. In **Italy**, 14% reported being not likely to adopt agroecological methods, while 50% expressed a somewhat likely stance and 36% were very likely to adopt them. In **Latvia**, 13% of respondents indicated they are not likely to adopt these practices, whereas 40% were somewhat likely and 47% expressed a very likely inclination. Similarly, **Lithuania** showed a favourable response, with 63% somewhat likely, and 37% very likely to adopt agroecological practices. Conversely, **Poland** exhibited a more cautious approach, with 14% of respondents not likely to adopt, a significant 73% somewhat likely, and only 14% very likely. In **Spain**, 18% of farmers reported being not likely to adopt these practices, 27% somewhat likely, and a notable 55% indicated they are very likely to do so. Lastly, **Turkey** showed the most scepticism, with 53% of respondents indicating they are not likely to adopt agroecological practices, 33% somewhat likely, and only 13% very likely.

Figure 3.4.2 Likelihood of future adoption of agroecological practices by country (n=151)

This data shows that some countries demonstrate strong support for adopting agroecological practices, others, particularly **Turkey**, show significant reluctance. This highlights the need for specific strategies to better promote sustainable farming practices in different contexts.

Key challenges and barriers to adopting agroecological practices

(Answer to “What challenges/barriers do you face in adopting agroecological practices?”)

The overall data indicates that a notable portion of respondents perceive a **lack of knowledge or training** as a barrier to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (a)). Specifically, 31% categorized this barrier as a moderate challenge, while 24% identified it as a significant challenge. Additionally, 17% viewed it as a considerable challenge, suggesting that it poses substantial obstacles. In contrast, 15% rated this barrier as not a challenge, and 14% considered it a minor challenge. Breaking this down by country, in **Czechia**, 43% of respondents perceived the barrier as a moderate challenge. Meanwhile, 21% viewed it as either a minor or considerable challenge, and 14% identified it as a significant challenge. In **Italy**, 36% indicated that this barrier was not a challenge, while 21% rated it as either a moderate or considerable challenge. In **Latvia**, 33% regarded it as a moderate challenge, with the remaining respondents evenly distributed across the scale. In **Lithuania**, 40% saw it as a moderate challenge, while 37% considered it a considerable challenge. In **Poland**, 36% felt it was not a challenge, and 32% rated it as a moderate challenge. In **Spain**, 36% viewed it as a significant challenge, while 18% each rated it as not a challenge, a minor challenge, or a moderate challenge. Lastly, in **Turkey**, 67% of respondents considered the lack of knowledge or training to be a significant challenge, highlighting its critical role in adopting agroecological practices.

The data shows that **limited financial resources** are perceived as a barrier to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (b)), with 48% of respondents categorizing this issue as a significant challenge and 26% as a considerable challenge. Additionally, 15% identified it as a moderate challenge, while 7% saw it as a minor challenge, and only 4% felt it was not a challenge at all. By country, in **Czechia**, 57% rated financial limitations as a significant challenge, with no respondents considering it a minor or not a challenge. In **Italy**, 43% viewed it as a significant challenge, and 21% rated it as a minor challenge. In **Latvia**, 40% considered it significant, while 37% saw it as a considerable challenge. In **Lithuania**, 30% identified it as significant and 33% as considerable. In **Poland**, 59% viewed financial constraints as significant, while in **Spain**, 55% considered it a considerable challenge. Finally, in **Turkey**, a notable 77% regarded limited financial resources as a significant challenge, underscoring its critical role as a barrier across all countries surveyed.

The data indicates that **resistance to change from conventional practices** is perceived as a barrier to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (c)), with 32% of respondents categorizing it as a significant challenge and 22% as a considerable challenge. Additionally, 26% rated it as a moderate challenge, while 10% viewed it as a minor challenge, and another 10% felt it was not a challenge at all. By country, in **Czechia**, 36% identified resistance to change as a significant challenge, with another 36% considering it considerable. In **Italy**, 36% felt it was not a challenge, while 29% rated it as moderate or considerable. In **Latvia**, 37% saw it as moderate, and 27% as considerable. In **Lithuania**, 40% rated it as moderate, with 33% considering it considerable. In **Poland**, 36% identified it as significant, while in **Spain**, 36% also viewed it as significant, with 27% feeling it was not a challenge. In **Turkey**, a notable 77% regarded resistance to change as a significant challenge, highlighting it as a major barrier across all countries surveyed.

The data shows that **uncertainty about implementation challenges** is perceived as a barrier to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (d)), with 31% of respondents categorizing it as a significant challenge and 24% as a considerable challenge. Additionally, 32% rated it as a moderate challenge, while 9% considered it a minor challenge and 5% felt it was not a challenge at all. Breaking this down by country, in **Czechia**, 43% of respondents viewed uncertainty as a moderate challenge, while 36% identified it as considerable and 14% as significant. In **Italy**, 21% felt it was not a challenge, and 29% rated it as moderate or considerable. In **Latvia**, 37% categorized it as significant, with 30% seeing it as considerable. In **Lithuania**, 43% viewed it as moderate, while 33% rated it as considerable and 13% as significant. In **Poland**, 45% identified it as a moderate challenge, while 32% considered it significant. In **Spain**, 36% viewed it as significant, and 27% rated it as moderate. Finally, in **Turkey**, 53% perceived uncertainty about implementation as a significant challenge.

The data reveals that **misconceptions about productivity or yield** are seen as barriers to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (e)). Overall, 30% of respondents categorized these misconceptions as a significant challenge, while 25% viewed them as considerable. Additionally, 31% rated them as a moderate challenge, 11% as a minor challenge, and 3% felt they were not a challenge at all. By country, in **Czechia**, 50% considered misconceptions a considerable challenge, and 29% viewed them as significant. In **Italy**, 43% identified them as significant, with 29% rating them as minor or moderate. In **Latvia**, 37% categorized them as moderate, while 27% viewed them as considerable. In **Lithuania**, 57% rated misconceptions as moderate, and 27% as considerable. In **Poland**, 45% regarded them as significant, with 32% rating them as considerable. In **Spain**, 36% saw them as moderate, and 27% as significant or considerable. In **Turkey**, 50% considered these misconceptions significant, with 27% rating them as moderate.

The data shows that **lack of support from agricultural authorities or institutions** is perceived as a barrier to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (f)). Overall, 45% of respondents rated this lack of support as a significant challenge, while 20% viewed it as a considerable challenge. Additionally, 21% categorized it as a moderate challenge, 10% as a minor challenge, and 5% felt it was not a challenge at all. Looking at the responses by country, in **Czechia**, 50% considered the lack of support a significant challenge, with 21% rating it as considerable. In **Italy**, 57% identified it as significant, with 21% viewing it as moderate or considerable. In **Latvia**, 43% categorized it as significant, while 27% rated it as considerable. In **Lithuania**, 40% viewed it as moderate, and 30% as significant. In **Poland**, 36% considered it significant, while 18% rated it as considerable. In **Spain**, 55% identified it as a considerable challenge, with 18% viewing it as significant. In **Turkey**, a notable 70% regarded the lack of support as significant.

The data indicates that **climatic or environmental constraints** are perceived as barriers to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (g)). Overall, 18% of respondents rated these constraints as a significant challenge, while 22% viewed them as considerable. Additionally, 32% categorized them as a moderate challenge, 18% as a minor challenge, and 10% felt they were not a challenge at all. By country, in **Czechia**, 29% considered climatic constraints significant, with another 36% rating them as considerable. In **Italy**, 29% also identified them as significant, and 36%

rated them as moderate. In **Latvia**, 33% categorized them as moderate, while 27% viewed them as considerable. In **Lithuania**, 37% saw climatic constraints as moderate, with 23% considering them considerable. In **Poland**, 18% viewed these constraints as not a challenge, while 32% rated them as minor and 14% as significant. In Spain, 45% considered them a moderate challenge, with 36% rating them as considerable. Lastly, in **Turkey**, 30% rated them as moderate and another 30% as considerable, with 20% viewing them as not a challenge.

The data reveals that **limited access to necessary equipment or inputs** is a significant barrier to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (h)). Overall, 32% of respondents rated this barrier as a significant challenge, while 30% viewed it as a considerable challenge. Additionally, 25% categorized it as a moderate challenge, 7% as a minor challenge, and another 7% felt it was not a challenge at all. By country, in **Czechia**, 43% considered limited access to equipment as a significant challenge, with 21% rating it as considerable. In **Italy**, 50% identified it as significant, while 29% viewed it as moderate. In **Latvia**, 47% categorized it as considerable, while 27% rated it as moderate. In **Lithuania**, 40% rated limited access as considerable, with 30% considering it moderate. In **Poland**, 55% regarded it as significant, while 18% rated it as moderate. In **Spain**, 64% considered it a moderate challenge, while 27% viewed it as considerable. Lastly, in **Turkey**, 53% rated it as significant, with 20% identifying it as moderate.

The data indicates that **land tenure or ownership issues** are perceived as barriers to adopting agroecological practices (Figure 3.4.3; Appendix 5 (i)). Overall, 23% of respondents rated these issues as a significant challenge, while 9% viewed them as a considerable challenge. Additionally, 19% categorized them as a moderate challenge, 14% as a mild challenge, and 36% felt they were not a challenge at all. By country, in **Czechia**, 36% considered land tenure issues a significant challenge, with 21% rating them as considerable. In **Italy**, 29% identified them as not a challenge, while 21% viewed them as mild. In **Latvia**, 40% rated land tenure issues as significant, while 33% categorized them as not a challenge. In **Lithuania**, 37% rated these issues as moderate, with 33% considering them mild. In **Poland**, 50% felt that land tenure was not a challenge, while 23% rated it as moderate. In **Spain**, 82% considered it not a challenge at all, with 9% viewing it as a considerable challenge. Lastly, in **Turkey**, 33% viewed land tenure issues as significant, while 10% rated them as considerable.

Figure 3.4.3 Evaluation of key challenges and barriers to adopting agroecological practices (n=151) (1 - Not a challenge; 2 - Minor challenge; 3 - Moderate challenge; 4 - Considerable challenge; 5 - Significant challenge)

The analyses indicate that multiple barriers coexist, with varying degrees of impact across different countries. Limited financial resources, limited access to equipment and lack of support from agricultural authorities and institutions are among the most pressing challenges identified by respondents. Addressing these barriers through financial support and institutional backing will be essential for supporting the transition to more sustainable agricultural practices. Land tenure issues appear to be less of a challenge, with a relatively even spread across ratings.

Several farmers shared additional concerns and misconceptions about agroecological practices. They pointed to challenges such as the difficulty of accessing markets for organic products and meeting consumer standards. Some farmers are sceptical about the effectiveness of practices like no-tillage, mentioning a lack of robust evidence. Economic viability and profitability also raised worries, particularly regarding market challenges and the high costs of implementing these practices, especially in terms of equipment compatibility. Farmers also highlighted issues with institutional support and bureaucratic barriers, often feeling that large agribusinesses hinder small farms from adopting sustainable methods. Some believe agroecology may not work well in certain regions due to local climate and economic conditions. Additionally, there is a feeling that the practices are often too generalized and not tailored to specific local needs, which leads to doubts about their effectiveness.

Farmers expressed a mix of practical and economic concerns, as well as a lack of trust and knowledge about the benefits of agroecology. There is a clear frustration over limited support from

institutions and markets, indicating a need for solutions that are more aligned with local challenges and enhance confidence in agroecological practices.

3.4.2. Facilitators

Key facilities to promote sustainable farming practices

(Answer to “What facilities would encourage you to adopt more sustainable farming practices?”)

The survey results on **access to financial support or incentives** show a strong consensus among farmers about its critical role in adopting sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (a)). Overall, 69% of respondents indicated that access to financial support is extremely important, underscoring the significant need for financial resources to help transition to more sustainable methods. In **Czechia**, 71% of farmers rated financial support as extremely important, with 14% considering it very important. In **Italy**, 57% expressed that it is extremely important, while 21% found it not important. Both **Latvia** and **Lithuania** reported that 67% of farmers viewed access to financial support as extremely important. In **Poland**, 55% acknowledged its extreme importance, with another 27% rating it as very important. Similarly, in **Spain**, 55% of respondents marked financial support as extremely important, with 27% considering it moderately important. **Turkey** reported an even stronger need, with 93% of farmers rating it as extremely important, highlighting the urgent demand for financial assistance in that context.

The survey results indicate that the **availability of training or educational programs** is viewed as crucial for adopting sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (b)), with 48% of respondents rating it as extremely important. In **Czechia**, 43% of farmers considered training moderately important, while 36% rated it as extremely important. **Italy** had a strong emphasis on training, with 64% marking it as extremely important. In **Latvia**, 37% found training extremely important, and 20% rated it moderately important. **Lithuania** reported that 43% viewed training as extremely important, with 30% considering it moderately important. In **Poland**, 27% saw training as extremely important, while another 27% rated it moderately important. In **Spain**, 36% deemed training availability as extremely important, with varied responses otherwise. **Turkey** showed the strongest preference, with 80% of farmers rating training as extremely important.

The survey results reveal that **supportive policies or regulations** are viewed as important facilitators for adopting sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (c)), with 51% of respondents considering them extremely important. In **Czechia**, 43% rated supportive policies as extremely important, while 29% saw them as moderately important. **Italy** reflected a similar pattern, with 43% marking them as extremely important and 21% as moderately important. In **Latvia**, 47% of respondents indicated supportive policies as extremely important, and 37% considered them very important. **Lithuania** had 40% rating supportive policies as extremely important and 33% as very important. In **Poland**, 41% viewed them as extremely important, with 36% rating them very important. **Spain** reported that 45% deemed supportive policies extremely important, alongside 27% who saw them as moderately important. **Turkey** showed the strongest preference, with 83% rating supportive policies as extremely important, indicating a significant need for regulatory support in the region.

The survey results indicate a strong desire for **support from agricultural authorities or institutions** in promoting sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (d)), with 55% of respondents rating this support as extremely important. In **Czechia**, 43% of participants rated the support from agricultural authorities as very important, while 36% considered it extremely important. **Italy** showed that 43% viewed this support as extremely important and 29% as very important. In **Latvia**, 63% marked this support as extremely important, with 27% rating it as very important. **Lithuania** had 47% considering support from agricultural institutions as extremely important, while 33% rated it as moderately important. In **Poland**, 41% viewed this support as extremely important, with an additional 27% rating it as very important. In **Spain**, 55% regarded the support as extremely important, with 27% considering it very important. **Turkey** had the highest percentage, with 80% of respondents rating institutional support as extremely important.

The survey results highlight the importance of **demonstrated benefits from other farmers or case studies** in encouraging the adoption of sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (e)), with 53% of respondents rating this factor as extremely important. In **Czechia**, 43% of participants considered the benefits demonstrated by other farmers as extremely important, while 14% viewed it as very important. In **Italy**, 57% rated this factor as extremely important, with 14% indicating it as very important. **Latvia** showed that 50% regarded these demonstrated benefits as extremely important, while 37% rated them as very important. In **Lithuania**, 53% of respondents viewed demonstrated benefits as extremely important, with 23% rating them as moderately important. In **Poland**, 50% rated these benefits as extremely important, and 18% considered them very important. **Spain** had 45% of participants viewing this factor as extremely important, with 27% marking it as very important. In **Turkey**, 63% rated the demonstrated benefits as extremely important, while 17% viewed them as very important.

The survey results indicate that **networking opportunities with other farmers practising sustainable methods** are regarded as a significant facilitator for adopting sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (f)). Overall, 41% of respondents rated this factor as extremely important. In **Czechia**, 36% of participants viewed networking opportunities as extremely important, while 29% rated them as moderately important. In **Italy**, 50% considered these opportunities extremely important, and 14% rated them as not important. **Latvia** had 43% of respondents rating networking as extremely important, with 30% indicating it as very important. **Lithuania** showed that 33% of respondents saw networking opportunities as extremely important, with 37% rating them as moderately important. In **Poland**, 27% rated these opportunities as extremely important, and 36% as moderately important. In **Spain**, 27% considered networking opportunities as extremely important, with a similar percentage rating them as very important. In **Turkey**, a substantial 60% rated networking with other sustainable farmers as extremely important.

The survey results regarding **access to affordable technology or equipment** show that this factor is seen as crucial for adopting sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (g)). Overall, 54% of respondents rated access to affordable technology as extremely important. In **Czechia**, 43% of respondents considered affordable technology as very important, while 36% rated it as extremely important. In **Italy**, a notable 64% rated it as extremely important, with an additional 21% considering it very important. **Latvia** reported 63% rating access to affordable technology as extremely important and 27% as very important. **Lithuania** had 33% of respondents rating access to technology as very important, with 27% considering it extremely important. In **Poland**, 55% rated it as extremely important, while 23% rated it as very important. In **Spain**, 36% of participants viewed access to technology as very important, with another 18% rating it as extremely important. In **Turkey**, an impressive 90% rated access to affordable technology as extremely important.

The survey results concerning **access to sustainable inputs, such as seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides**, reveal varying perceptions among respondents regarding the importance of adopting sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (h)). Overall, 44% of participants rated access to sustainable inputs as extremely important. In **Czechia**, 43% of respondents considered access to sustainable inputs as very important, with 29% rating it as extremely important. In **Italy**, half of the respondents rated it as extremely important. **Latvia** reported similar results, with 50% considering it extremely important and 23% as very important. In **Lithuania**, 30% rated access to sustainable inputs as moderately important, with 27% considering it extremely important. **Poland** had 36% rating it as extremely important, while 45% deemed it very important. In **Spain**, 55% rated it as very important, but only 9% considered it extremely important. In **Turkey**, a significant 80% rated access to sustainable inputs as extremely important.

The survey results regarding **the assurance of maintained or improved productivity** reveal varied perceptions among respondents about the importance of adopting sustainable farming practices (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (i)). Overall, 52% of participants rated the assurance of productivity as extremely important. In **Czechia**, 50% of respondents indicated that assurance of productivity was extremely important, with an additional 36% rating it as very important. In **Italy**, 57% considered it

extremely important. **Latvia** showed a similar trend, with 50% of respondents rating it as extremely important and 37% as very important. In **Lithuania**, 27% rated the assurance of productivity as moderately important, with 30% considering it extremely important. **Poland** had 36% of respondents rating it as extremely important, while another 36% considered it very important. In **Spain**, 55% viewed assurance of productivity as extremely important, and 36% as very important. **Turkey** had a striking 83% rating it as extremely important, highlighting a strong emphasis on productivity assurance among farmers there.

The survey results concerning **farmers' concerns about environmental impact** reveal varying levels of significance attributed to this issue across different countries (Figure 3.4.4; Appendix 6 (j)). Overall, 25% of respondents rated environmental impact as extremely important, while 36% rated it as slightly important. In **Czechia**, 29% considered environmental impact to be extremely important, while 36% rated it as very important. In **Italy**, 36% identified it as extremely important, with 43% marking it as very important. **Latvia** showed that 20% of respondents rated it extremely important, with 33% considering it very important. In **Lithuania**, concerns about environmental impact were expressed by 47% as moderately important, while 17% rated it as extremely important. In **Poland**, a significant 73% viewed it as moderately important, with only 9% rating it as extremely important. In **Spain**, 55% of respondents rated environmental concerns as moderately important, and 18% deemed it extremely important. Lastly, in **Turkey**, 47% identified it as extremely important, but only 3% rated it as very important.

Figure 3.4.4 Evaluation of key facilities to promote sustainable farming practices (n=151) (1 - Not important; 2 - Slightly important; 3 - Moderately important; 4 - Very important; 5 - Extremely important)

Financial support, supportive policies, affordable equipment and institutional backing are critical enablers of agroecological adoption. While still relevant, environmental concerns are rated lower than other practical and financial facilitators.

Farmers identified several facilitators for the successful adoption of sustainable farming practices. A key theme was the need for fair market regulation to prevent price manipulation by wholesalers and ensure equitable compensation for sustainably produced goods. Many respondents stressed the importance of financial incentives, such as tax relief and grant programs. Additionally, farmers emphasized the role of consumer awareness campaigns to promote understanding of sustainable agricultural practices and their environmental benefits. There was also a strong call for regulatory measures that penalize polluters, reflecting a desire for policies that ensure environmental accountability. Respondents highlighted the importance of access to decision support systems (DSS) and resources from agricultural universities, research institutions, and farmer organizations, which are crucial for the practical implementation of sustainable practices. Another recurring concern was the need to guarantee profitability during the transition to sustainable methods.

The responses indicate a demand for an integrated support framework encompassing market regulation, financial assistance, consumer education, and access to scientific and practical knowledge to facilitate the widespread adoption of sustainable farming practices.

3.5. Section 5: Soil-Related Challenges

Most effective agroecological practices for addressing soil-related challenges

(Answer to “Please evaluate, which agroecological practices are most effective for addressing soil-related challenges?”)

Evaluating agroecological practices rated by farmers for their effectiveness in addressing soil-related challenges such as maintaining soil organic carbon (SOC), preventing emissions, mitigating peat degradation, combating salinization and acidification, reducing erosion and contamination, addressing soil sealing, and enhancing soil biodiversity, water storage capacity, nutrient retention, and optimal soil structure provides valuable insights into the methods farmers consider most effective for specific issues (Figure 3.5.1).

Maintaining or increasing soil organic carbon (SOC)

Farmers recognize **organic farming** (8%), **crop rotation** (8%), and **agroecological farming** (7%) as the most effective practices for enhancing soil organic carbon (SOC), along with **cover cropping** (6%) and **perennial crops** (6%). However, the effectiveness of these practices is debated. While some studies indicate that organic farming can increase SOC annually (Leifeld and Fuhrer, 2010), others question this due to methodological concerns in research. Recommended management practices like crop rotations, conservation tillage, cover crops, and agroforestry have been shown to enhance SOC accumulation (Jarecki and Lal, 2003; Koushika et al., 2024), but their effectiveness varies with factors such as climate change, soil type, and management techniques (Gollany and Venterea, 2018). More rigorous studies with proper baselines and consistent measurements are needed to evaluate the impact of different farming practices on SOC (Leifeld and Fuhrer, 2010). Notably, crop rotations and cover crops are recognized for SOC sequestration (Jarecki and Lal, 2003; Stavi and Lal, 2010), while perennial crops, particularly in agroforestry systems, are promising for enhancing sustainability and SOC capacity (Stavi and Lal, 2010). Regenerative agriculture practices, such as no-till and increased use of perennials, show SOC increases compared to conventional methods (Rehberger et al., 2023).

Avoiding emissions

Farmers identify **agroecological farming** (9%), **biological nitrogen fixation** (8%), **organic farming**, **no-tillage farming**, and **agroforestry** (7%) as the most effective practices for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, particularly nitrous oxide (N₂O). These practices reduce reliance on synthetic nitrogen fertilizers, which are linked to high emissions of N₂O, a potent greenhouse gas. Biological nitrogen fixation through legume crops in organic systems shows potential for reducing nitrogen limitations and enhancing sustainability (Barbieri et al., 2022). Organic farming can also lower greenhouse gas emissions by eliminating synthetic fertilizers and increasing soil organic carbon (Holka et al., 2022). However, certain agroecological practices, including the use of organic fertilizers and reduced tillage, can occasionally lead to increased N₂O emissions depending on specific conditions. Additionally, technology-driven solutions like enhanced-efficiency fertilizers and biochar have demonstrated significant mitigation potential (Grados et al., 2022). Organic agricultural techniques, including no-till cropping, agroforestry, and integrated crop-animal farming, provide valuable strategies for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Niggli et al., 2009).

Avoiding peat degradation

Water management techniques (11%) are the most highly rated practices for protecting peatlands, followed by **organic farming**, **agroecological farming**, **crop rotation**, **perennial crops**, and **organic matter/nutrient management** (8%). Peatland degradation is primarily driven by drainage for agriculture and forestry, leading to increased carbon dioxide emissions and soil compaction (Liu et al., 2023; Leifeld et al., 2020). Effective water management helps conserve

peatlands by increasing soil humidity, reducing evaporation, and maintaining groundwater levels (Lestari and Mukhlis, 2021). In addition to water management, organic farming, and crop rotation are recognized as effective strategies for protecting peatlands (Liu et al., 2023). However, even after rewetting, degraded soils may still release high levels of nitrous oxide (Liu et al., 2019). To restore degraded peatlands, interventions such as rewetting, shading, reprofiling, mowing, grazer control, and active revegetation are recommended (Rowland et al., 2021). Transitioning to sustainable peatland management requires significant changes in land and water practices, along with adequate financial and policy support (Liu et al., 2023).

Avoiding soil salinization

Soil salinization poses a significant threat to global agriculture and food security (Singh, 2021; Sahab et al., 2021). Various management strategies have been proposed to combat this issue. **Water management techniques** (19%) were strongly preferred for combating salinization, given their role in managing irrigation practices and drainage to prevent salt accumulation in the soil (Minhas et al., 2020; Dong, 2012). **Agroecological and organic farming** (11%) and **organic matter/nutrient management** (8%) were also helpful in managing soil health to reduce salinity risks. Agroecological approaches, such as crop selection, genetic improvements, and agroforestry, can enhance plant tolerance to salinity. Organic matter and nutrient management, including the use of chemical amendments, biochar, and microbial inoculants, can improve soil properties and mitigate salinity effects (Sahab et al., 2021).

Avoiding soil acidification

Farmers identified **agroecological farming** (15%) as the top approach for managing soil acidification, followed by **organic matter/nutrient management** (12%) and **crop rotation** alongside **organic farming** (9%). These practices can balance soil pH and enhance nutrient availability in acidic soils. Soil acidification poses a challenge in agriculture, lowering productivity and yields due to synthetic fertilizer overuse, which leads to nitrate leaching and nutrient imbalances (Obiri-Nyarko, 2012; Tkaczyk et al., 2020). Agroecological approaches, such as diverse crop rotations and organic nutrient inputs, support soil pH by fostering nutrient cycling and decreasing dependency on synthetic inputs (Toncea et al., 2015). Traditional practices, including lime application, effectively neutralize soil acidity by increasing soil base saturation and buffering acidic conditions (Obiri-Nyarko, 2012). Biochar has shown potential for improving acidic soils due to its liming effect, which raises pH while enhancing soil fertility (Bolan et al., 2023; Dai et al., 2017). Integrating biochar with these organic amendments can enhance soil health and stabilize pH. Optimized nitrogen management, which involves applying nitrogen in suitable amounts with site-specific techniques, has proven effective in reducing acidification risks by enhancing nutrient uptake and minimizing nitrate leaching (Miao et al., 2011; Zeng et al., 2017). Integrating agroecological practices with innovative nutrient management technologies offers a balanced approach to addressing soil acidification, with the potential to enhance agricultural productivity (Cherie and Abeje, 2022).

Avoiding soil erosion

Farmers identified **cover cropping** (10%), **soil conservation techniques**, **no-till farming**, **perennial crops** (9%), and **crop rotation** (7%) as effective strategies for preventing soil erosion. Soil erosion is a significant environmental challenge that diminishes water-holding capacity, soil organic matter, and biodiversity (Zuazo and Pleguezuelo, 2008). Effective conservation management practices could significantly reduce soil erosion. Specifically, cover cropping, no-till farming, and crop rotation can decrease water runoff and erosion, as a result increase crop yield (Derpsch et al., 1986; Du et al., 2021). Establishing plant covers is one of the most effective measures for controlling erosion and promoting soil regeneration (Zuazo and Pleguezuelo, 2008). Additionally, these conservation practices enhance soil health indicators, such as soil organic carbon, aggregation, and infiltration. However, the effectiveness of these techniques can vary depending on soil texture, with

coarse- and medium-textured soils exhibiting better improvements than fine-textured soils (Du et al., 2021).

Avoiding soil contamination

Farmers identified **organic farming** (15%) and **integrated pest management** (14%) as the most effective approaches for preventing soil contamination. By minimizing synthetic chemical inputs and adopting natural alternatives, these practices significantly reduce the risk of pollutants entering the soil. Research indicates that both organic farming and integrated pest management are effective in avoiding soil contamination and promoting soil health. Organic farming has been shown to improve soil composition, enhance biodiversity, and increase soil carbon stocks over the long term (Yadav et al., 2024). While some pesticides and organic contaminants were still found in soils managed with integrated pest management, their levels were low and similar to or lower than those in conventional farming areas (Plaza-Bolaños et al., 2012). This suggests that while integrated pest management reduces the presence of contaminants, it may not eliminate them. Organic pest management techniques, including crop rotation and the promotion of beneficial insects, effectively control pest populations while reducing reliance on chemical pesticides and supporting soil health and ecological balance (Saxena, 2021).

Avoiding soil sealing

Farmers rated **organic farming** (11%), **soil conservation techniques** (9%), and practices like **crop rotation, agroforestry, and agroecological farming** (8%) as essential for preventing soil sealing, which occurs when soil loses its natural functions due to compaction and construction activities. While there is substantial research on the effects of soil sealing, studies on soil unsealing and restoration remain limited (Tobias et al., 2018). While there is no evidence that agroecological practices can directly address soil sealing, farmers are adopting conservation agriculture methods such as reduced tillage, no-tillage, cover cropping, agroforestry, intercropping, and diversified crop rotations. Their primary motivation is to preserve soil fertility; however, they face challenges related to crop management, machinery, and yield performance as they aim to improve soil fertility, enhance soil quality, and minimize environmental impacts (Paracchini et al., 2020; Ryan and Peigné, 2017; Casagrande et al., 2016; Peigné et al., 2016; Virto et al., 2015).

Enhancing soil biodiversity

Crop rotation (13%), **cover cropping** (9%), **organic farming, and intercropping** (8%) are effective methods for enhancing soil biodiversity by promoting a diverse ecosystem of soil organisms through continuous plant cover, increased organic matter, and reduced chemical inputs. Research shows that these practices improve soil microbial communities and functions, with crop rotations significantly boosting soil carbon, nitrogen, and microbial biomass, essential for soil quality and productivity (Bender et al., 2016; McDaniell et al., 2014). Organic farming practices also enhance biodiversity and soil quality, which are essential for sustainable food production (Underwood et al., 2011). Techniques of conservation tillage and intercropping with legumes improve microbial activity and diversity (Njira and Nabwami, 2013). Collectively, these practices support soil health and sustainable crop production through better nutrient cycling (Njira and Nabwami, 2013).

Enhancing water storage capacity

Water management techniques (14%), **crop rotation** (11%), **organic farming** (10%), and **organic matter/nutrient management** (9%) are recognized as effective practices for improving soil water retention. The relationship between soil organic matter (SOM) and available water capacity (AWC) is complex. While some studies indicate that increasing SOM can enhance water retention and AWC (Huntington, 2007; Lal, 2020), others argue that the effect is limited, especially in clay soils (Minasny and McBratney, 2018). SOM improves water retention due to its hydrophilic nature and ability to enhance soil structure and porosity (Huntington, 2007). Management practices like

conservation agriculture, cover cropping, and residue mulching can restore SOM and potentially increase AWC (Lal, 2020). Additionally, the effectiveness of practices such as crop rotation and irrigation vary significantly across regions (Anton et al., 2021).

Enhancing soil nutrient retention

Farmers identified **crop rotation** (14%), **organic farming** (10%), **organic matter/nutrient management** (9%), and **biological nitrogen fixation** (8%) as effective practices for enhancing soil nutrient retention. These strategies can significantly improve natural soil processes and contribute to nutrient retention (Hamel et al., 2004). Crop rotation is a key practice in organic farming, integrating soil fertility maintenance with crop and livestock production to promote nutrient cycling and diversity. By alternating crops, farmers can mitigate nutrient depletion and improve soil health through varied root systems that enhance soil structure and biological activity, thereby increasing nutrient availability. Additionally, effective organic matter management enhances soil structure and boosts biological activity, which are crucial for nutrient supply and overall system health (Watson et al., 2002). Biological nitrogen fixation by legumes plays a pivotal role in replenishing nitrogen levels in the soil, reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers and enhancing nutrient retention in organic systems (Watson and Stockdale, 2013).

Optimal soil structure

Crop rotation (13%), **organic farming**, and **organic matter/nutrient management** (10%) were highlighted as practices that support optimal soil structure. These practices improve soil aggregation and porosity, allowing for better air and water movement, which is crucial for plant root development and overall soil health. Crop rotation, organic matter management, and other organic farming practices support optimal soil fertility and structure (Watson et al., 2002). Additionally, crop rotations, tillage, and avoiding compaction are important for maintaining optimal soil structure (Ball et al., 2005). Organic farming generally enhances soil conservation by increasing soil organic matter content, improving soil structure and aggregate stability, enhancing water retention, and reducing erosion compared to conventional farming (Shepherd et al., 2002; Pulleman et al., 2003; Erhart and Hartl, 2009). These benefits are attributed to regular organic matter inputs, diverse crop rotations, and extended periods of soil cover (Erhart and Hartl, 2009).

Soil compaction

One notable soil challenge not directly addressed in the questionnaire is soil compaction; however, it was mentioned by some farmers in additional comments. Agroecological practices can effectively mitigate soil compaction and enhance soil health within agricultural systems. Key strategies for preventing compaction include reducing machinery pressure on soil, optimizing soil moisture during operations, and implementing controlled traffic (Hamza and Anderson, 2005). Increasing soil organic matter through the retention of crop residues and diverse crop rotations with deep-rooted plants can improve soil structure (Hamza and Anderson, 2005; Ryan and Peigné, 2017). Combining practices such as compost application, recycling pruning residues, and cover cropping can significantly enhance soil water content, organic matter, and nutrient levels (Hrameche et al., 2024). Other beneficial approaches include reduced tillage, organic fertilization, and the integration of semi-natural landscape elements. While some of these practices are already well integrated into agricultural systems, others, such as intercropping, agroforestry, and the use of allelopathic plants, hold potential for broader implementation to improve soil health and promote overall agricultural sustainability (Wezel et al., 2014).

Lack of awareness

A significant proportion of farmers were not aware or unsure about certain practices, particularly polyculture and permaculture, indicating a knowledge gap. Increasing awareness and education about these practices could further enhance their adoption and effectiveness.

The data demonstrates that farmers view organic farming, water management techniques, organic matter and nutrient management, crop rotation, and agroecological farming as highly effective for addressing various soil-related challenges. These practices are seen as valuable for improving soil organic carbon, preventing erosion, managing salinity, and enhancing nutrient retention. However, gaps in awareness and understanding of specific practices like polyculture and permaculture suggest a need for further education and training to increase their adoption and effectiveness. This comprehensive perspective on soil-related challenges underscores the multifaceted benefits of adopting agroecological practices to ensure long-term soil health and sustainability.

Figure 3.5.1 Evaluation of most effective agroecological practices for addressing soil-related challenges

4. Conclusions

1. The demographic and farm information gathered from 151 respondents across seven countries reveals key insights into the agricultural landscape. The age distribution indicates a predominantly middle-aged workforce, suggesting the need for succession planning and strategies to attract younger farmers. Gender disparity points to a significant male predominance, reflective of broader trends in the sector. Educational backgrounds are diverse, with a substantial number of respondents holding university degrees, highlighting the potential for innovative agricultural practices. The farming experience is varied, with a balanced representation of both seasoned and newer farmers, promoting knowledge exchange.
2. The analysis of farm size reveals a trend towards larger operations, particularly in countries like Czechia, Latvia, and Poland, while Turkey stands out for its concentration of small and medium-sized farms. Agricultural land use practices show a strong focus on arable farming, particularly in Turkey, contrasted with Italy's emphasis on permanent crops. The majority of respondents reported no livestock presence, indicating a preference for specialized crop production. This study underscores the importance of continuous education, adaptation to environmental challenges, and the need for policies that support diverse farming practices across different regions.
3. The findings from the survey on agroecological practices and current farming methods highlight a significant awareness and recognition of the importance of sustainable agriculture among farmers. While a substantial portion of respondents demonstrated familiarity with agroecological practices, revealing a generally positive perception of their significance in modern farming, the data also indicates notable gaps in understanding and adoption. The strong recognition of practices such as crop rotation and legume cultivation points to a foundation upon which further education and support can be built.
4. Conventional practices, such as deep ploughing and precision herbicide application, remain prevalent, suggesting that traditional methods continue to dominate despite the growing interest in sustainability. The mixed assessments of environmental friendliness among farmers underscore the need for targeted initiatives to promote agroecological methods more effectively.
5. The variations in awareness and perception across different countries highlight the necessity for tailored approaches to education and policy that consider local contexts. While progress is evident in some countries, still remains substantial potential for enhancing the adoption of environmentally friendly practices across all regions. Ultimately, fostering a deeper understanding of agroecological principles, coupled with incentives and support for sustainable practices, will be crucial in advancing the overall environmental sustainability of agricultural systems.
6. The awareness and implementation of agroecological practices among farmers vary significantly across different techniques and countries. While well-established practices like crop rotation, organic farming, and no-till farming enjoy higher familiarity and adoption rates—indicating a solid foundation within the farming community—less conventional practices such as permaculture, polyculture, and agroforestry are notably less recognized and utilized. This disparity highlights the need for targeted educational initiatives and resources to enhance knowledge and encourage the adoption of innovative agroecological practices, ultimately supporting sustainable agricultural development.
7. The findings underscore a critical need for enhanced training and education in agroecological practices among farmers, as a significant majority (75%) report lacking formal education in

this area. While certain countries demonstrate better engagement in agroecological training, the overall low levels of participation highlight barriers to accessing knowledge and resources. Farmers primarily rely on a mix of online platforms, agricultural extension services, and personal networks for information, indicating a diverse approach to learning but also revealing gaps in systematic educational support. To foster wider adoption of sustainable farming methods, there is a pressing necessity for targeted training programs and improved access to educational resources tailored to the specific needs of farmers across different regions. Addressing these gaps will not only empower farmers with the knowledge and skills needed for sustainable agriculture but also contribute to the overall resilience and sustainability of the agricultural sector.

8. The analysis highlights significant barriers to the adoption of agroecological practices among farmers, including limited financial resources, lack of training and support, and resistance to changing conventional methods. A notable proportion of farmers express scepticism about the effectiveness of these practices and face challenges related to market access and equipment compatibility. While many farmers show a positive inclination towards adopting agroecological methods, addressing these barriers is crucial for facilitating their transition to sustainable agriculture. Tailored support from agricultural authorities, alongside increased access to resources and training, is essential to empower farmers and foster a broader acceptance of agroecological practices across various regions.
9. The survey results underscore the vital role of financial support, training, supportive policies, and access to affordable technology in facilitating the adoption of sustainable farming practices among farmers across various countries. While environmental concerns remain significant, practical and financial enablers are prioritized. Farmers call for an integrated support framework that includes fair market regulations, financial incentives, consumer awareness, and access to research and decision-making resources to ensure a smooth transition to sustainability. This multifaceted approach is essential for promoting the widespread adoption of sustainable agricultural practices and ensuring both environmental and economic viability.
10. The evaluation of agroecological practices by farmers reveals a strong consensus on their effectiveness in addressing critical soil-related challenges. Key practices such as organic farming, water management techniques, organic matter and nutrient management, crop rotation, and agroecological farming are viewed as essential for enhancing soil organic carbon, preventing erosion, managing salinity, and improving nutrient retention. These approaches collectively contribute to long-term soil health, sustainability, and resilience against environmental stressors.
11. The identified knowledge gaps regarding practices such as polyculture and permaculture highlight an important area for development. Enhancing education and awareness among farmers about these and other effective practices is crucial for maximizing the potential of agroecological systems. As farmers increasingly recognize the interconnectedness of soil health and agricultural productivity, targeted training and resources can empower them to adopt a broader array of sustainable practices. This fosters healthier soils and contributes to the overall sustainability of agricultural systems. Such a holistic approach benefits individual farms while also promoting ecological balance and food security amid ongoing environmental challenges.

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Appendix 1. Template of questionnaire for farmers

Section 1: Demographic Information

1.1 Personal Information

- Name of the farmer (optional)
- Age
 - ✓ <35
 - ✓ 35-64
 - ✓ >65
- Gender
 - ✓ Male
 - ✓ Female
- Education level
 - ✓ Primary school
 - ✓ High school
 - ✓ University (Bachelor's degree)
 - ✓ University (Master's degree)
 - ✓ University (PhD degree)
 - ✓ Other
- Have you attended any farming-related courses?
 - ✓ Yes → If "Yes", please specify
 - ✓ No
- Years of farming experience
 - ✓ <5
 - ✓ 5-10
 - ✓ 10-20
 - ✓ 20-30
 - ✓ >30
- Country (list of countries)
 - ✓ Austria
 - ✓ Belgium
 - ✓ Czechia
 - ✓ France
 - ✓ Denmark
 - ✓ Estonia
 - ✓ Finland

- ✓ Germany
 - ✓ Hungary
 - ✓ Ireland
 - ✓ Italy
 - ✓ Latvia
 - ✓ Lithuania
 - ✓ The Netherlands
 - ✓ Norway
 - ✓ Poland
 - ✓ Portugal
 - ✓ Slovakia
 - ✓ Slovenia
 - ✓ Spain
 - ✓ Sweden
 - ✓ Switzerland
 - ✓ Turkey
 - ✓ United Kingdom
- Environmental zone (according to Metzger et al., 2005)

1.2 Farm Information

- Farm size
 - ✓ 0 ha
 - ✓ <2 ha
 - ✓ 2-4,9 ha
 - ✓ 5-9,9 ha
 - ✓ 10-19,9 ha
 - ✓ 20-29,9 ha
 - ✓ 30-49,9 ha
 - ✓ 50-99,9 ha
 - ✓ >100 ha
- Agricultural area utilization
 - ✓ arable land
 - ✓ permanent grassland
 - ✓ permanent crops
 - ✓ kitchen gardens

- ✓ unutilised agricultural area
- ✓ other
- Livestock presence (if applicable)
 - ✓ Yes → If "Yes", please specify major livestock type
 - ✓ No
- List of major livestock types
 - ✓ Cattle
 - ✓ Pigs
 - ✓ Goats
 - ✓ Sheep
 - ✓ Poultry
 - ✓ Other

Section 2: Ecological Identity

2.1 Perception of Agroecological Practices

- How familiar are you with the definition of agroecological practices?
 - ✓ Very familiar
 - ✓ Somewhat familiar
 - ✓ Not familiar at all

Please read the statement below.

Agroecological practices involve applying ecological principles to agricultural systems to create sustainable and resilient farming methods. These practices aim to optimize the use of natural resources, minimize environmental impact, and promote biodiversity.

Examples of agroecological practices include crop rotation, intercropping, cover cropping, agroforestry, integrated pest management, water conservation techniques such as rainwater harvesting and drip irrigation, soil conservation methods like contour plowing and terracing, and the use of organic fertilizers and composting to enhance soil health.

Additionally, agroecological approaches may involve promoting beneficial insect populations, utilizing native plant species for landscaping and erosion control, and implementing holistic grazing management in livestock systems. These practices collectively contribute to building resilient agricultural systems that are less reliant on external inputs and more in harmony with natural ecosystems.

These agroecological practices can vary in their application depending on the specific context, climate, and goals of a particular farming system. Adopting a combination of these practices can contribute to more sustainable and resilient agriculture.

- Evaluate the significance of agroecological practices in modern farming:
 - ✓ Extremely important
 - ✓ Very important

- ✓ Moderately important
- ✓ Somewhat important
- ✓ Not important
- Practices considered to be agroecological by farmers:
 - ✓ Crop rotation
 - ✓ More cereals
 - ✓ More legume crops
 - ✓ More grassland
 - ✓ Intercropping/multiple cropping
 - ✓ Cover/catch crops
 - ✓ Perennial crops
 - ✓ Permanent grazing
 - ✓ Rotational grazing
 - ✓ Zero grazing
 - ✓ No till
 - ✓ Non-inversion/reduced tillage
 - ✓ Non-inversion/minimum tillage
 - ✓ Non inversion tillage
 - ✓ Deep ploughing
 - ✓ Contour ploughing
 - ✓ Terrace farming
 - ✓ Controlled traffic farming
 - ✓ Reduced/more precise mineral fertiliser application
 - ✓ Appropriate compost application
 - ✓ Appropriate farmyard manure application
 - ✓ Biochar application
 - ✓ Incorporation of crop residues
 - ✓ Fertilisation plan/advice
 - ✓ Better manure storage
 - ✓ Manure treatment
 - ✓ Valorisation of waste streams
 - ✓ Enhanced weathering
 - ✓ Mechanical weeding
 - ✓ Precision herbicide application
 - ✓ Organic farming

- ✓ Agroecological farming
- ✓ Precision agriculture
- ✓ Agroforestry
- ✓ Conservation agriculture
- ✓ Other

2.2 Current Farming Practices

- Briefly describe your current farming practices OR select from list below.
- Select the practices that are relevant for your farm:
 - ✓ Crop rotation
 - ✓ More cereals
 - ✓ More legume crops
 - ✓ More grassland
 - ✓ Intercropping/multiple cropping
 - ✓ Cover/catch crops
 - ✓ Perennial crops
 - ✓ Permanent grazing
 - ✓ Rotational grazing
 - ✓ Zero grazing
 - ✓ No till
 - ✓ Non-inversion/reduced tillage
 - ✓ Non-inversion/minimum tillage
 - ✓ Non inversion tillage
 - ✓ Deep ploughing
 - ✓ Contour ploughing
 - ✓ Terrace farming
 - ✓ Controlled traffic farming
 - ✓ Reduced/more precise mineral fertiliser application
 - ✓ Appropriate compost application
 - ✓ Appropriate farmyard manure application
 - ✓ Biochar application
 - ✓ Incorporation of crop residues
 - ✓ Fertilisation plan/advice
 - ✓ Better manure storage
 - ✓ Manure treatment

- ✓ Valorisation of waste streams
 - ✓ Enhanced weathering
 - ✓ Mechanical weeding
 - ✓ Precision herbicide application
 - ✓ Organic farming
 - ✓ Agroecological farming
 - ✓ Precision agriculture
 - ✓ Agroforestry
 - ✓ Conservation agriculture
 - ✓ Other
- To what extent do you consider your farming practices to be environmentally friendly?
 - ✓ Very environmentally friendly
 - ✓ Moderately environmentally friendly
 - ✓ Somewhat environmentally friendly
 - ✓ Not environmentally friendly

Section 3: Awareness of Agroecological Practices

3.1 Knowledge Level

- On a scale of 1 to 5, please indicate how familiar you are with the following agroecological practices?

Agroecological practices	1 - Never heard of it	2 - Heard of it but not familiar	3 - Somewhat familiar	4 - Moderately familiar	5 - Implement this practice
Crop rotation					
Polyculture					
Intercropping					
Companion planting					
Agroforestry					
Cover cropping					
Perennial crops					
Permaculture					
Rotational grazing					
Livestock integration					
Agroecological farming					
Organic farming					
No-till farming					

Biological nitrogen fixation					
Soil conservation techniques					
Water management techniques					
Organic matter/nutrient management					
Integrated pest management					
Mechanical weeding					
Other					

- If "Other", please specify.

3.2 Information Sources

- Have you received any training or education on agroecological practices?
 - ✓ Yes
 - If “Yes”, please specify what kind of training/workshop you attended.
 - If “Yes”, please specify where you found information about training/workshop.
 - ✓ No
- Where do you usually seek information about agricultural practices?
 - ✓ Academic journals and research articles
 - ✓ Books and publications
 - ✓ Agricultural extension services (government agencies, universities, and non-profit organizations)
 - ✓ Online resources
 - ✓ Conferences and workshops
 - ✓ Other

Section 4: Barriers and Facilitators

4.1 Barriers to Adoption

- How likely are you to adopt a combination of agroecological practices on your farm in the future?
 - ✓ Very likely
 - ✓ Somewhat likely
 - ✓ Not likely
- What challenges/barriers do you face in adopting agroecological practices? *Please allocate points on a scale from 1 to 5 to indicate the extent to which each barrier poses a challenge for you. 1 representing "Not a challenge" and 5 representing "Significant challenge."*

List of challenges and barriers	1	2	3	4	5
Lack of knowledge or training					
Limited financial resources					
Resistance to change from conventional practices					
Uncertainty about implementation challenges					
Misconceptions about productivity or yield					
Lack of support from agricultural authorities or institutions					
Climatic or environmental constraints					
Limited access to necessary equipment or inputs					
Land tenure or ownership issues					

- Do you have other concerns or misconceptions regarding agroecological practices?
 - ✓ Yes → If "Yes", please specify.
 - ✓ No

4.2 Facilitators

- What facilities would encourage you to adopt more sustainable farming practices? *Please allocate points on a scale from 1 to 5 to indicate the importance of each facilitator in encouraging you to adopt more sustainable farming practices. 1 representing "Not important" and 5 representing "Extremely important."*

Facilitators	1	2	3	4	5
Access to financial support or incentives					
Availability of training or educational programs					
Supportive policies or regulations					
Support from agricultural authorities or institutions					
Demonstrated benefits from other farmers or case studies					
Networking opportunities with other farmers practicing sustainable methods					
Access to affordable technology or equipment					
Access to sustainable inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides					
Assurance of maintained or improved productivity					
Concerns about environmental impact					

- Do you consider any other support systems or resources beneficial in facilitating the adoption of more sustainable farming practices?
 - ✓ Yes → If "Yes", please specify.
 - ✓ No

Section 5: Soil-Related Challenges

- Please evaluate, which agroecological practices are most effective for addressing soil-related challenges?

Soil challenges	Maintain/increase SOC	Avoid emissions	Avoid peat degradation	Avoid salinisation	Avoid acidification	Avoid erosion	Avoid contamination	Avoid soil sealing	Enhance soil biodiversity	Enhance water storage capacity	Enhance soil nutrient retention	Optimal soil structure	I am not aware/I don't know
Crop rotation													
Polyculture													
Intercropping													
Companion planting													
Agroforestry													
Cover cropping													
Perennial crops													
Permaculture													
Rotational grazing													
Livestock integration													
Agroecological farming													
Organic farming													
No-till farming													
Biological nitrogen fixation													
Soil conservation techniques													
Water management techniques													
Organic matter/nutrient management													
Integrated pest management													
Mechanical weeding													
Other													

Appendix 2. Environmental zones of Europe (according to Metzger et al., 2005)

Appendix 3. List of definitions used in questionnaire

Crop rotation – Alternating the types of crops grown in a specific field over time to improve soil fertility, reduce pest and disease pressure, and prevent nutrient depletion.

Polyculture – Farming practice where multiple crops are grown together in the same field without a distinct spatial arrangement, promoting biodiversity and reducing the risk of crop failure.

Intercropping – Farming practice where two or more crops are grown simultaneously in a defined spatial arrangement within the same field, optimizing resource use and enhancing crop interactions.

Companion planting – Growing different plant species near to enhance nutrient uptake, deter pests, and maximize space utilization.

Agroforestry – Integrating trees and shrubs into agricultural systems to enhance biodiversity, improve soil fertility, provide shade, and offer additional sources of income.

Cover cropping – Planting cover crops during periods when the main crop is not growing to protect and improve soil structure, suppress weeds, and add organic matter.

Perennial crops – Plants that live for more than two years and can produce harvestable yields over multiple growing seasons without needing to be replanted each year.

Permaculture – Designing agricultural systems based on ecological principles, emphasizing the use of natural patterns and minimizing waste.

Rotational grazing – Livestock management method where animals are moved through different sections of pasture on a rotational basis to optimize forage use, prevent overgrazing, and improve soil health.

Livestock integration – Combining crop and livestock farming to enhance nutrient cycling, improve soil fertility, and diversify income streams.

Agroecological farming – Agricultural system that applies ecological principles to farming practices, emphasizing biodiversity, soil health, and ecosystem services.

Organic farming – Avoiding synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, and genetically modified organisms (GMOs), and instead relying on organic inputs and natural processes.

No-till farming – Minimizing soil disturbance by avoiding traditional ploughing, which helps retain soil structure, moisture, and microbial activity.

Biological nitrogen fixation – Encouraging the growth of nitrogen-fixing plants (e.g., leguminous plants, such as soybeans, peas, and clover) or using nitrogen-fixing bacteria to improve soil fertility without relying on synthetic fertilizers.

Soil conservation techniques – Practices implemented in agriculture to prevent soil erosion and maintain soil fertility. Examples include contour ploughing, which involves ploughing along the contour lines of a slope to reduce water runoff, and terracing, which creates level platforms on sloping land to reduce soil erosion and retain water.

Water management techniques – Methods used to efficiently collect, distribute, and conserve water in agriculture. Examples include rainwater harvesting, which involves collecting and storing rainwater for later use, and drip irrigation, a system that delivers water directly to the roots of plants, minimizing water waste.

Organic matter/nutrient management – Application of compost and manure to improve soil fertility and health in agricultural systems. This practice enhances nutrient availability, soil structure, and microbial activity, promoting sustainable crop growth.

Integrated pest management (IPM) – Combining biological, cultural, and mechanical methods to manage pests and diseases, minimizing reliance on chemical inputs.

Mechanical weeding – Method of weed control in agriculture that involves the use of mechanical devices, such as cultivators, hoes, or weeders, to physically remove weeds from fields. This approach avoids the use of herbicides.

Appendix 4. Evaluation of farmers' knowledge levels of agroecological practices by country

a - Crop rotation; b – Polyculture; c – Intercropping; d - Companion planting

e)

f)

g)

h)

■ 1 - Never heard of it ■ 2 - Heard of it but not familiar ■ 3 - Somewhat familiar ■ 4 - Moderately familiar ■ 5 - Implement this practice

e – Agroforestry; f - Cover cropping; g - Perennial crops; h – Permaculture

■ 1 - Never heard of it ■ 2 - Heard of it but not familiar ■ 3 - Somewhat familiar ■ 4 - Moderately familiar ■ 5 - Implement this practice

i - Rotational grazing; j - Livestock integration; k - Agroecological farming; l - Organic farming

■ 1 - Never heard of it ■ 2 - Heard of it but not familiar ■ 3 - Somewhat familiar ■ 4 - Moderately familiar ■ 5 - Implement this practice

m - No-till farming; n - Biological nitrogen fixation; o - Soil conservation techniques; p - Water management techniques

■ 1 - Never heard of it ■ 2 - Heard of it but not familiar ■ 3 - Somewhat familiar ■ 4 - Moderately familiar ■ 5 - Implement this practice

q - Organic matter/nutrient management; r - Integrated pest management; s - Mechanical weeding

Appendix 5. Evaluation of key challenges and barriers to adopting agroecological practices by country

a - Lack of knowledge or training; b - Limited financial resources; c - Resistance to change from conventional practices; d - Uncertainty about implementation challenges

1 2 3 4 5

(1 - Not a challenge; 2 - Minor challenge; 3 - Moderate challenge; 4 - Considerable challenge; 5 - Significant challenge)

e - Misconceptions about productivity or yield; f - Lack of support from agricultural authorities or institutions; g - Climatic or environmental constraints; h - Limited access to necessary equipment or inputs

Appendix 6. Evaluation of key facilities to promote sustainable farming practices by country

(1 - Not important; 2 - Slightly important; 3 - Moderately important; 4 - Very important; 5 - Extremely important)

a - Access to financial support or incentives; b - Availability of training or educational programs; c - Supportive policies or regulations; d - Support from agricultural authorities or institutions

e)

f)

g)

h)

■ 1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5

(1 - Not important; 2 - Slightly important; 3 - Moderately important; 4 - Very important; 5 - Extremely important)

e - Demonstrated benefits from other farmers or case studies; f - Networking opportunities with other farmers practicing sustainable methods; g - Access to affordable technology or equipment; h - Access to sustainable inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides

■ 1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5

(1 - Not important; 2 - Slightly important; 3 - Moderately important; 4 - Very important; 5 - Extremely important)

i - Assurance of maintained or improved productivity; j - Concerns about environmental impact